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Development of a CNN for the Identification of Low Surface Brightness Galaxies

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Once men turned their thinking over to machines in the hope that this would set them free. But that only permitted other men with machines to enslave them.

– **Frank Herbert**, *Dune*

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Abstract

The detection and classification of *low surface brightness* (LSB) galaxies plays a critical role in understanding the formation and evolution of the universe. However, traditional observational techniques often face challenges in identifying these faint objects due to their low *signal-to-noise* ratio and their frequent overlap with brighter astronomical sources. In this thesis, we present the development and implementation of a *Convolutional Neural Network* (CNN) made for the detection of LSB galaxies in astronomical images.

This work is divided into two parts. The first part provides a theoretical foundation, introducing the concept of LSB galaxies and reviewing neural networks, with a specific focus on CNNs and their role in image processing tasks.

The second part transitions into a practical framework, presenting *PyTorch* as the primary tool for the development and training of deep learning models. After exploring some example applications of CNNs using *PyTorch*, the design and implementation of the CNN made for the detection of LSB galaxies are detailed. The proposed model is trained on a synthetic dataset of galaxy images based on *Euclid* data, augmented with realistic noise and stars.

Extensive testing on simulated datasets demonstrates the model's ability to accurately recognize faint galaxies with high precision and generalization, outperforming traditional methods. The CNN achieves an 84.5% success rate in identifying galaxies with *integrated magnitude* values between 22 and 24, with even better results for higher luminosities. However, performance drops drastically for magnitudes between 24 and 26, which is the exact range where background noise becomes dominant.

In summary, this work highlights the potential of CNNs as a tool in the field of astrophysics, enabling a more effective search of astronomical object and contributing to a deeper understanding of the cosmos.

Abstract in italiano

La rilevazione e la classificazione delle *galassie a bassa luminosità superficiale* (LSB) hanno un ruolo cruciale nella comprensione della formazione e dell'evoluzione dell'universo. Tuttavia, le tecniche osservative tradizionali incontrano spesso difficoltà nell'identificare questi deboli oggetti deboli a causa del loro basso *rapporto segnale-rumore* e della frequente sovrapposizione con sorgenti astronomiche più luminose. In questa tesi, presentiamo lo sviluppo e l'implementazione di una *Rete Neurale Convolutionale* (CNN) progettata per il rilevamento di *galassie a bassa luminosità* in immagini astronomiche.

Questo lavoro è diviso in due parti. La prima parte fornisce una base teorica, introducendo il concetto di *LSB galaxies* e descrivendo le caratteristiche principali delle reti neurali, con particolare attenzione alle CNN e al loro ruolo nell'elaborazione delle immagini.

La seconda parte si concentra sullo sviluppo, presentando *PyTorch* come strumento principale per la creazione e l'addestramento di modelli di *deep learning*. Dopo aver esplorato alcune applicazioni esemplificative delle CNN con *PyTorch*, vengono descritti il design e l'implementazione della CNN per il rilevamento delle *galassie a bassa luminosità superficiale*. Il modello proposto viene addestrato su un dataset di immagini simulate di galassie basato su dati della missione *Euclid*, con l'aggiunta di un rumore, realistico, e di stelle.

I test approfonditi su dataset simulati dimostrano la capacità del modello di riconoscere accuratamente le galassie deboli con elevata precisione e generalizzazione, superando i metodi tradizionali. La CNN raggiunge un tasso di successo dell'84,5% nell'identificazione di galassie con *magnitudine integrata* compresa tra 22 e 24, con risultati persino superiori per luminosità più elevate. Tuttavia, le prestazioni calano drasticamente per magnitudini tra 24 e 26, ovvero nell'intervallo in cui il rumore di fondo diventa predominante.

In sintesi, questo lavoro evidenzia il potenziale delle CNN nel campo dell'astrofisica, consentendo una ricerca più efficace degli oggetti astronomici e contribuendo a una comprensione più approfondita dell'Universo.

Part I

Theoretical framework

Introduction to Low Surface Brightness Galaxies

In this chapter we present the main features of *low surface brightness* galaxies.

1.1 Low Surface Brightness Galaxies

A **low-surface-brightness galaxy**, or **LSB galaxy**, is a celestial object that is significantly dimmer than the typical galaxies we observe. By definition, their *surface brightness* is at least an order of magnitude fainter than the night sky, usually below 23 mag/arcsec^2 [1].

LSB galaxies are elusive objects due to their faint appearance. The systematic study of these objects began only in the 1980s when significant improvements in observational techniques were made. The first and largest LSB galaxy to be identified and confirmed is *Malin 1*, discovered in 1986[2]. Notably, it is still considered one of the largest spiral galaxies ever discovered (as shown in Figure 1.1), with a diffuse disk that stretches over 650000 light-years in diameter, much larger than the *Milky Way*, which spans about 100000 light-years.

Figure 1.1: Image of *Malin 1* taken during the *Sloan Digital Sky Survey*, processed image by G. Donatiello, showing its extensive arm structure.[41]

In recent years, LSB galaxies have been discovered in many different environments and sizes. Some, for example, are satellites of nearby galaxies, such as *Pisces VII/Triangulum III* for *M33*[3], and satellites of the *Milky Way*, while others are isolated or nearly isolated galaxies like *Donatiello I*[4]1.2. Some are even members of massive galaxy clusters like *Virgo* and *Coma*. With this in mind, it is crucial to understand that current models suggest that LSB galaxies could represent a significant portion of the total galaxy population, with estimates ranging from 15% to 50% of all galaxies in the universe.

Figure 1.2: *Donatiello I* (Do I) captured by *Telescopio Nazionale Galileo* (TNG). This dwarf galaxy was found on 23 September 2016 in a deep wide field amateur image of the *Andromeda galaxy* region obtained from the composition of a set of images taken during several years with a refractor ED127mm by the italian amateur astronomer Giuseppe Donatiello. The detection was confirmed by a visual inspection of the SDSS DR9 images and follow-up observations using the professional facilities TNG and GTC (La Palma, Spain).[42]

1.2 Main features of LSB galaxies

Apart from the defining feature of faintness, LSB galaxies appear to have a higher proportion of dark matter relative to their visible matter [1]. Although these galaxies seem to have an abundance of neutral hydrogen gas, they show a very low rate of star formation. One possible reason for this could be that LSB galaxies are frequently found in isolated regions of space. As a result, interactions with other galaxies, which could trigger star formation, are rare. Therefore, LSB galaxies may be an essential tool to understand the galactic evolution and could challenge current and future theories, particularly the *Lambda-CDM model*¹.

¹**Lambda-CDM** (Λ CDM) model is a model of the Big Bang theory with three major components:

1.3 Classical methods for the search for LSB galaxies

The classical methods for detecting LSB galaxies involve several observational techniques that focus on improving sensitivity to faint objects. Few are reported in this paragraph.

1. Deep Optical Surveys

In the of optical surveys, it's highly preferable to improve the image quality to greatest extent. An option is to use **Long Exposure Imaging** as longer exposure allows for the collection of more light, making it possible to detect galaxies with low surface brightness. However, this method is limited by the sensitivity of photographic plates and modern CCDs to faint objects. Another possibility is the **Enhanced Image Processing**, a technique that involve image stacking and contrast enhancement to make LSB galaxies more visible. These methods involve combining multiple images to increase the *signal-to-noise ratio*.

2. Neutral Hydrogen (HI) Surveys

These methods usually involve **radio observations** since LSB galaxies are often rich in neutral hydrogen (H I). So radio telescopes that can detect the 21cm emission line of hydrogen are useful for identifying these galaxies. Surveys like those conducted by the *Arecibo Radio Telescope*² have been successful in detecting LSB galaxies based on their gas content rather than their starlight [5].

3. Surface Brightness Limit Studies

Historically, LSB galaxies were missed because surveys were biased towards higher surface brightness objects. In response, specialized surveys designed to detect galaxies with surface brightness well below the standard detection threshold have been developed. These surveys set a lower *detection limit* on surface brightness, helping to uncover a population of faint, extended objects like LSB galaxies.

-
- a cosmological constant (Λ), associated with dark energy;
 - the postulated cold dark matter (CDM);
 - ordinary baryonic matter.

It's considered the current standard model of Big Bang cosmology as it provide a good agreement with current observation.

²The **Arecibo Telescope** was a 305 m radio telescope built into a natural sinkhole located near Arecibo, Puerto Rico. It was the world's largest single-aperture telescope for more than 50 years. The instrument, damaged by hurricanes and earthquakes, suffered the collapse of its suspended structure on December 1, 2020, leading to its destruction, with a decision in 2022 not to rebuild it.

4. Photographic Plate Techniques

Early searches for LSB galaxies used photographic plates with **emulsions** that were particularly sensitive to faint light. David Malin’s discovery of *Malin 1* was achieved using this method by enhancing further photographic images[5].

5. Sky Surveys with Lower Resolution Thresholds

Several large-scale sky surveys, such as the **Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS)**³, have also contributed to the discovery of LSB galaxies by providing large datasets that can be mined for faint objects. By lowering the surface brightness threshold in data analysis, researchers have been able to identify more LSB galaxies.

1.3.1 Experimental limits

Due to the faint nature of LSB galaxies, they have been difficult to detect, as previously mentioned. Many challenges and experimental limitations exist. Obviously, many telescopes are optimized for detecting brighter objects, and many LSB galaxies are also obscured by the sky background noise. As a result, many past surveys were biased toward the detection of *high surface brightness* (HSB) galaxies, both due to the limitations of detection equipment and the selection criteria used. This led to selection biases and an underestimation of the LSB population.

LSB galaxies, which are often large and diffuse, might also have their faint outskirts missed in observations made with telescopes that have relatively narrow fields of view, leading to incomplete detection (and possible misclassification) or total omission from catalogs. In denser regions of the sky, crowding from brighter objects, like stars, can easily overshadow faint LSB galaxies.

In the case of radio observations, classical H I surveys had limited resolution and sensitivity, which restricted their ability to detect LSB galaxies at large distances or with very low gas content.

A possible solution to many of these problems is using *Neural Networks* (discussed in Chapter 5) for the search and classification of LSB galaxies. In particular, in this work we will discuss the use of **Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN)**, which are described in Chapter 3. A CNN can automatically learn and extract relevant features from complex and noisy datasets, such as astronomical images. In the case of LSB galaxies, which have faint and diffuse light profiles, neural networks can be trained to identify subtle features that are difficult for traditional image processing techniques to capture and can detect faint structures, such as LSB galaxies, even when they are barely distinguishable from the background noise. Moreover, modern astronomical surveys generate enormous amounts of data (e.g., from *Euclid*, see section 1.5.1), making

³The **Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS)** is a multi-spectral imaging and spectroscopic survey using a dedicated 2.5m telescope at Apache Point Observatory in New Mexico, United States.

it impractical to analyze them manually. Neural networks can also be retrained and fine-tuned as new data becomes available and can provide probabilistic outputs, helping to prioritize galaxies that are more likely to be LSBs and warrant further study. Neural networks can simultaneously analyze data across multiple wavelengths (e.g., optical, infrared, radio), allowing for a more comprehensive detection strategy.

1.4 Current and future surveys

In this section, we will briefly discuss some of the current and future surveys that aim to discover new LSB galaxies, with a major focus on the *Euclid* mission, because our simulated data, as we will discuss in the final chapter, are based on its observations.

1.4.1 Legacy Survey of Space and Time (LSST)

Figure 1.3: Rendering of the completed LSST (Legacy Survey of Space and Time) at Vera Rubin Observatory. The LSST’s primary instrument will be an 8.4-meter wide-field telescope with a 3.2-gigapixel camera. [43]

The **Legacy Survey of Space and Time (LSST)**, conducted by the *Vera C. Rubin Observatory*, is one of the most promising current projects for the study of LSB galaxies. The observatory, currently under construction, is located on Cerro Pachón, a 2,682-meter-high mountain in the Coquimbo Region, in northern Chile, alongside the existing *Gemini South* and *Southern Astrophysical Research Telescopes*. The LSST Base Facility is located about 100 kilometers (62 miles) away from the observatory by road, in

the town of La Serena[6]. The observatory is named after Vera Rubin, an American astronomer who pioneered discoveries about galaxy rotation rates and dark matter[7]. The **Legacy Survey of Space and Time (LSST)** (Figure 1.3) is a planned 10-year survey. The data will enable researchers worldwide to better evaluate a wide range of pressing questions about the nature of dark energy and dark matter, the formation of the *Milky Way*, the properties of small bodies in the solar system, the trajectories of potentially hazardous asteroids, and the possible existence of undiscovered phenomena.

1.4.2 Dragonfly Telephoto Array

The **Dragonfly Telephoto Array** is a telescope system designed specifically to detect ultra-low surface brightness objects. It uses an array of commercially available telephoto lenses with highly sensitive detectors. Dragonfly has already made significant discoveries in the field of LSB galaxy detection and will continue to be a vital tool for observing faint galaxies and extended stellar halos.

Notable Dragonfly discoveries include *Dragonfly 44*, a galaxy roughly as massive as the *Milky Way*, with 99.9% of its mass composed of dark matter, and *NGC 1052-DF2*, whose measurements with other instruments initially suggested it was a galaxy with very little dark matter. Follow-up studies with the *Hubble Space Telescope* have shown a possible deficiency in dark matter, though not as originally thought.

1.4.3 James Webb Space Telescope

As the largest telescope in space, the **James Webb Space Telescope's** incredible sensitivity in both the optical and infrared spectra makes it an effective tool for observing faint, diffuse galaxies like LSB galaxies. JWST's high-resolution imaging will allow detailed studies of the internal structure of nearby LSB galaxies, helping to investigate their stellar populations and dark matter distribution.

1.4.4 Square Kilometre Array (SKA)

The **Square Kilometer Array (SKA)** is a massive radio telescope array that will be capable of detecting neutral hydrogen gas in galaxies with great sensitivity. LSB galaxies, which are often rich in gas but faint in optical light (1.3), will be key targets for SKA's surveys. It will help map the distribution of gas in these galaxies, offering insights into their formation and evolution.

1.5 Euclid Mission

1.5.1 Euclid

Euclid is a wide-angle space telescope with a 600 megapixel camera to record visible light, a near-infrared spectrometer, and a photometer to determine the redshift of detected galaxies. It was developed by the *European Space Agency (ESA)* and the *Euclid Consortium*, and was launched on 1 July 2023 from Cape Canaveral in Florida[8]. *Euclid* is designed to explore the evolution of the dark Universe. It will make a 3D map of the Universe (with time as the third dimension) by observing billions of galaxies out to 10 billion light-years, across more than a third of the sky. By comparing the statistical properties and morphology of the large-scale structure (LSS) with simulations and theoretical models, we can infer how the Universe expanded, study how matter structures formed, and ultimately, predict the Universe’s fate. The Euclid mission will achieve this primarily using two complementary methods: *weak gravitational lensing* and *galaxy clustering*.

Weak lensing uses a specific aspect of General Relativity: mass bends light rays similarly to optical lenses. The distortions encode how much matter the light rays encountered on their way to us and can thus be used to map the matter distribution[9].

Galaxies are luminous tracers of the matter distribution. However, to reconstruct their true 3D distribution, we need to measure galaxy distances. This is possible using the cosmological redshift, which is induced by cosmological expansion and is directly proportional to the galaxy’s distance from us. The inhomogeneity on different scales in these maps will then be quantified through specific statistics of the density fluctuations and used to constrain model predictions.

1.5.2 History of the mission

Euclid emerged from two mission concepts proposed in response to the *ESA’s Cosmic Vision 2015–2025 Call for Proposals*, issued in March 2007: *DUNE (Dark UNiverse Explorer)*, and *SPACE (SPectroscopic All-sky Cosmic Explorer)*. Both missions proposed complementary techniques to measure the geometry of the Universe, and after an assessment study phase, a combined mission resulted. The new mission concept was called *Euclid*, after the Greek mathematician Euclid of Alexandria (300 BC), and was formally adopted in 2012. ESA selected *Thales Alenia Space’s* Italian division for the construction of the satellite in Turin, while the payload module was the responsibility of *Airbus Defence and Space’s* French division in Toulouse. An international consortium of scientists, the *Euclid Consortium*, comprising scientists from 13 European countries and the United States, provided the *Visible-Light Camera (VIS)* and the *Near-Infrared*

Spectrometer and Photometer (NISP).

After Russia withdrew in 2022 from the Soyuz-planned launch of *Euclid*, the *ESA* reasigned it to a *SpaceX Falcon 9* launch vehicle, which launched on 1 July 2023 from *Cape Canaveral Space Launch Complex 40*. Thirty days after launch, *Euclid* began orbiting the Sun-Earth Lagrangian point L2 in an eclipse-free halo orbit about 1 million km wide.

Figure 1.4: An artistic depiction of the *ESA*'s *Euclid* spacecraft in space. *Euclid* carries a 1.2-meter telescope designed to capture light from distant objects like far-off galaxies. This light is then focused onto two scientific instruments onboard: the visible camera (VIS), which captures incredibly sharp images, and the near-infrared spectrometer and photometer (NISP), which provides both images and spectroscopic data, covering the largest infrared field of view ever seen from space.^[44]

1.5.3 Spacecraft

The *Euclid* spacecraft (Figure 1.4) is approximately 4.7 m tall and 3.7 m in diameter. It consists of two major components: the service module and the payload module.

The payload module comprises a 1.2 m diameter telescope and two scientific instruments: a visible-wavelength camera (the *VISible instrument*, VIS) and a near-infrared camera/spectrometer (the *Near-Infrared Spectrometer and Photometer*, NISP). The service module contains the satellite systems: electric power generation and distribution, attitude control, data processing electronics, propulsion, telecommand and telemetry, and thermal control.

Instruments

- **VIS**, a camera operating at visible wavelengths (530–920 nm) made of a mosaic of charge-coupled detectors, containing 600 million pixels, allows measurement of the deformation of galaxies.

- **NISP**, a camera composed of mosaic detectors sensitive to near-infrared light radiation (920–2020 nm) with 65 million pixels. It's designed to provide low-precision measurements of redshifts and uses a slitless spectrometer to analyze the spectrum of light in the near-infrared (920–1850 nm), to acquire precise redshifts and distances of millions of galaxies with an accuracy 10 times better than photometric redshifts, and to determine the baryon acoustic oscillations.

An overview of Neural Networks

In this chapter we will introduce the concept of Neural Network, the concept of *perceptron* and we'll examine a basic architecture following the text-book *The Scientist and Engineer's Guide to Digital Signal Processing* by Steven W. Smith[10].

2.1 Target detection

Scientists frequently need to identify whether a particular object or condition is present. For instance, geophysicists search for oil deposits, doctors diagnose diseases, and astronomers hunt for a galaxy in a picture. Typically, this requires comparing collected data to a certain threshold: if the data surpasses the threshold, the object or condition is deemed to exist.

Consider a medical device that screens for cancer by displaying a value ranging from 0 to 30 when applied to a patient. Lower numbers suggest a healthy patient, while higher numbers imply the potential presence of cancerous tissue. However, the device is not flawless and can sometimes give incorrect results. How should this system be used to best serve the patient?

Now, imagine using this device on two groups: healthy individuals and individuals diagnosed with cancer. The outcomes are displayed in histograms, where the healthy group typically shows lower values, while the cancer group shows higher ones, though there is some overlap. These histograms represent estimates of the *probability distribution function* (pdf). For example, a healthy person might have an 8% likelihood of receiving a score of 3, while a 1% chance exists for a score of 18.

When the device is used on a patient with unknown health status, and a value of 15 is obtained, we know that a healthy individual has a 2.1% probability of this result, while a cancer patient has a 0.7% probability. Hence, the patient is three times more likely to be healthy, indicating a 25% probability of having cancer, assuming no other information is factored in.

Figure 2.1: Relationship between ROC curves and pdf. Reprinted from *The Scientist and Engineer's Guide to Digital Signal Processing* by Steven W. Smith, 1997, p. 455. Copyright 1997 by California Technical. [45]

However, this evaluation is incomplete without considering the general prevalence of cancer in the population. If only one out of a thousand people has cancer, these probabil-

ities must be adjusted. This adjustment is done by scaling the probability distributions, leading to a significantly different interpretation of the test result. For example, a value of 15 might correspond to just a 0.025% likelihood of having cancer, instead of 25%. Despite such probability-based analysis, most situations require a binary yes/no decision. This is achieved by comparing the test result to a pre-set threshold. If the result exceeds the threshold, the test is considered positive; otherwise, it is negative. This threshold selection leads to outcomes such as true positives, true negatives, false positives, and false negatives. Determining the optimal threshold involves balancing the reduction of false positives and false negatives.

The **Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve** (Figure 2.1) is a tool that helps in assessing this trade-off by plotting the true positive rate against the false positive rate for varying threshold values. A more effective detection process will bend the ROC curve toward the upper-left corner, while random guessing results in a diagonal 45-degree line. Adjusting the threshold will affect the proportions of false positives and false negatives.

In complex detection systems that use multiple parameters, such as x-ray imaging for cancer diagnosis, combining factors like size and brightness can enhance detection accuracy. Instead of setting individual thresholds for each parameter, a more sophisticated method involves analyzing a multi-dimensional parameter space to differentiate between targets and non-targets.

This process requires two main steps: **feature extraction**, which reduces raw data into significant parameters such as size, brightness, and edge clarity. These parameters are often referred to as **features** or **classifiers**. Feature extraction helps reduce the volume of data. The second step is **evaluation**, which uses these parameters to determine whether the target condition is present. This approach can be extended into multi-dimensional spaces, or **hyperspaces**, which are mathematically similar to one, two, or three-dimensional spaces, although they are more difficult to visualize and manipulate.

In conclusion, scientists and engineers rely on comparing data to thresholds to detect specific conditions. Techniques such as probability analysis, ROC curves, and multi-parameter spaces play a crucial role in improving detection systems. These methods are essential in developing efficient diagnostic tools, such as those used for cancer screening.

2.2 Neural Networks

Figure 2.2: Neural network architecture. This is a classic neural network with three layers and fully interconnected nodes. The input layer simply passes data to the next layer without any changes. Then the hidden and output layers process the data by modifying it based on specific rules. Reprinted from *The Scientist and Engineer's Guide to Digital Signal Processing* by Steven W. Smith, 1997, p. 459. Copyright 1997 by California Technical. [45]

Humans and other animals process information through neural networks, which consist of trillions of neurons communicating via short electrical impulses called action potentials. When computer algorithms simulate these biological systems, they are called **artificial neural networks**. However, the term **neural network** is often used interchangeably to describe both biological and artificial systems.

There are two key reasons for studying neural networks: to better understand how the human brain works and to develop computers that can solve complex, abstract, or poorly defined problems. For example, traditional computers struggle with tasks like speech recognition and face identification, areas in which humans naturally excel.

A variety of neural network designs have been investigated. Some are inspired by the structures observed in biological studies, while others are based on mathematical models. The most widely used neural network model consists of three **layers**: the *input layer*, the *hidden layer*, and the *output layer*, as depicted in Figure 2.2. Each layer contains nodes (shown as small circles), and the lines between them represent the direction of

information flow. In this type of network, data moves in a single direction, from the input layer to the output layer.

The nodes in the input layer are *passive*, meaning they do not alter the data—they simply accept a value and pass it unchanged to multiple outputs. In contrast, the nodes in the hidden and output layers are *active*, meaning they process and modify the input data. Other types of neural networks may have more intricate structures, such as feedback loops that allow information to flow in different directions.

Each input value is copied and sent to all hidden layer nodes in what is called a fully interconnected structure. At the hidden nodes, these input values are multiplied by weights—predefined numbers stored in the system. The weighted inputs are summed to generate a single output, denoted by the symbol Σ in the diagram Figure 2.3. Before this sum is passed on, it is processed through a nonlinear function called a **sigmoid**, an "S"-shaped curve that limits the output of each node (described in Subsection 2.2.1). Although the *sigmoid* function can accept any real number as input, its output always falls between 0 and 1.

Figure 2.3: This diagram explains how the hidden and output layers process inputs. Each input is multiplied by a specific weight, and the results are added together to create a single output. This output is then passed through a *sigmoid*, which transforms the value into a smooth, "S"-shaped range. Edited from *The Scientist and Engineer's Guide to Digital Signal Processing* by Steven W. Smith, 1997, p. 461. Copyright 1997 by California Technical. [45]

The outputs from the hidden layer are represented by variables like z . These values are then duplicated and sent to the next layer. In the output layer, active nodes combine and modify the inputs to produce the final output of the network.

Neural networks can have various numbers of layers and nodes per layer. Many practical applications employ a three-layer structure, with up to several hundred input nodes. The hidden layer usually contains about 10% of the number of nodes in the input layer. For tasks such as target detection, the output layer often requires just one node, with its output being thresholded to indicate whether or not a target is present in the input

data. This architecture is both simple and flexible, making it suitable for a wide range of problems. The key to its performance lies in selecting appropriate weights, which marks a significant departure from traditional computing that relies on step-by-step algorithms.

Consider, for example, a neural network designed to recognize handwritten digits. A collection of images, each showing a handwritten number, is stored on a computer. How does the system determine whether the images represent the digits 0 through 9? Traditional image processing techniques might use algorithms such as *edge detection* or *template matching*¹. In contrast, with a neural network, the pixel values of the images are fed into the input layer, and the output layer generates corresponding values. By fine-tuning the weights, the network can be trained to classify each image correctly, indicating whether the digit is 0, 1, 2, and so on, up to 9.

By adjusting the weights, the network's output could also be configured to classify objects as metal or nonmetal, biological or non-biological, enemy or ally, etc. Unlike traditional methods, there are no predefined algorithms, rules, or step-by-step procedures—just a relationship between the input data and output determined by the selected weights.

```

10 'NEURAL NETWORK (FOR THE FLOW DIAGRAM IN FIG. 2.2)
11 '
12 DIM X1[15]      'stores input values
13 DIM X2[4]      'stores values after processing by the hidden layer
14 DIM X3[2]      'stores values after processing by the output layer
15 DIM WH[4,15]   'stores weights for the hidden layer
16 DIM WO[2,4]    'stores weights for the output layer
17 '
18 GOSUB XXXX      'hypothetical subroutine to load X1[ ]
                   with input data
19 GOSUB XXXX      'hypothetical subroutine to load weights
                   WH[ , ] & WO[ , ]
20 '
21 '              'COMPUTE VALUES FOR THE HIDDEN NODES, X2[ ]
22 FOR J% = 1 TO 4 'loop for each hidden node
23     ACC = 0     'reset accumulator variable, ACC
24     FOR I% = 1 TO 15 'multiply and sum each input value
                           with its weight
25         ACC = ACC + X1[I%] * WH[J%,I%]
```

¹**Edge detection** is an image processing technique that identifies points in an image where brightness changes dramatically, effectively detecting the outlines and structural edges of objects. **Template matching** instead compares a predefined template against different regions of the target image; systematically slides the template across the image, calculating similarity metrics to determine the best match.

```

26     NEXT I%
27     X2[J%] = 1 / (1 + EXP(-ACC) ) 'apply sigmoid to the sum
28 NEXT J%
29 '
30 '           'COMPUTE VALUES FOR THE OUTPUT NODES, X3[ ]
31 FOR J% = 1 TO 2 'loop for each output node
32     ACC = 0     'reset accumulator variable, ACC
33     FOR I% = 1 TO 4 'multiply and sum each hidden node's output with
                    its weight
34         ACC = ACC + X2[I%] * WO[J%,I%]
35     NEXT I%
36     X3[J%] = 1 / (1 + EXP(-ACC) ) 'apply sigmoid to the sum
37 NEXT J%
38 '
39 END

```

2.2.1 Activation function

An **activation function** is a fundamental element of neural networks, responsible for introducing non-linearity into the models and enabling the learning of complex relationships in the data. In general, an *activation function* transforms the output of each neuron into a specific range, influencing the behavior and learning capabilities of the network. One of the most common activation functions is the already mentioned **sigmoid**, shown alongside its derivative in Figure 2.4 and mathematically defined as:

$$s(x) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-x}} \quad (2.1)$$

The specific form of the sigmoid is not critical; what matters is that it acts as a smooth threshold function. To explain, a simple threshold function outputs a value of 1 when $x > 0$ and 0 when $x < 0$. The sigmoid function performs similarly but has the advantage of being differentiable. Its derivative plays a crucial role in finding optimal weights. More details on this process will be discussed later.

One of the *sigmoid* function's advantages is that its derivative has a shortcut for calculation:

$$s'(x) = s(x)[1 - s(x)] \quad (2.2)$$

An interesting observation is the possibility of introducing a bias or horizontal shift to center the *activation function* at a value other than $x = 0$. This is achieved by adding a special node at the input layer with a constant value (referred as *bias node*). This node, multiplied by a specific weight, introduces an offset (*DC offset*) that allows greater flexibility in the network's behavior.

Finally, it is important to note that without non-linear *activation functions*, a neural network would be equivalent to a simple linear model, regardless of the number of layers. For example, considering a three-layer network as shown in Figure 2.2, the absence of *activation functions* would reduce the network to a two-layer structure, eliminating the ability to learn non-linear representations. Other than sigmoid, there are other *activation functions*, such as *ReLU*, which is discussed in Appendix A.

Figure 2.4: Python plots of the sigmoid function (left) and its derivative (right).

2.2.2 Learning algorithm

Neural networks determine the necessary weights for a given task through a **learning algorithm** that processes **examples** of the desired system behavior. In the sonar problem, for instance, the algorithm would use a dataset containing numerous sample segments, such as echoes from submarines, whales, and background noise. From this data, the learning algorithm calculates a set of weights that allow the network to perform the task effectively. While this process is called **learning**, it is more precisely the *optimization of weights* based on the statistical properties of the examples. However, the final weights often appear random to human observers and are difficult to interpret, even though they enable the neural network to produce the correct input-output relationships. This lack of transparency can make neural networks seem mysterious, however they are generally considered properly understood.

In fact, we first show that neural network weights can be chosen using traditional *Digital Signal Processing* (DSP) methods. Following this, we demonstrate that learning algorithms can produce even better results than conventional approaches, reinforcing confidence in the method, even though it may not explain precisely why a particular set of weights works.

From a more advanced perspective, a neural network functions by labeling different

regions within a high-dimensional *parameter space*. Consider a *sonar neural network* with 1000 inputs and a single output. By selecting appropriate weights, the output will approach 1 if the input signal is from a submarine and 0 if it is just noise. This task can be viewed as navigating a 1000-dimensional parameter space, with each point in this space representing a possible input. A theoretical look-up table could store every output for each input combination, but this would be computationally infeasible. Instead, a neural network computes these values using significantly fewer weights, making the architecture's effectiveness depend on how efficiently it partitions this hyperspace with a limited number of weights.

This viewpoint also suggests how many nodes might be required in the hidden layer. A parameter space with N dimensions requires N values to specify a location, and distinguishing between regions in this space demands $2N$ values (minimum and maximum along each axis, forming a rectangular volume). However, in most practical applications, the number of regions required is much smaller than the total number of dimensions, explaining why hidden layers are often only 2% to 30% the size of the input layer.

Another way to understand neural networks is through the DSP concept of *correlation*. Correlation is the optimal technique for identifying a known pattern within a signal by multiplying the signal by the desired pattern and summing the results. The higher the sum, the more the signal matches the pattern. Now, think of each hidden node as searching for a specific pattern in the input data by correlating the inputs with its associated weights. If the pattern is present, the output of the hidden node will be high; otherwise, it will be low.

The *activation function* plays a key role in this framework. If we were to design a neural network manually, the output of each hidden node could represent the *fractional probability* that a given pattern is present in the input. The output layer would then repeat this process, effectively forming a network that searches for *patterns of patterns*, making it a complex correlation system.

Neural networks can also perform fundamental DSP operations like *convolution* (see 3) and *Fourier analysis*, and even more complex tasks. For example, consider filtering an N -sample signal to produce another N -sample output signal. In convolution, each output sample is a weighted sum of the input samples, a process that can be replicated by a two-layer neural network with N nodes in each layer. If each output node uses the same weights, the network can implement linear convolution. Similarly, the *Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT)* can be performed by correlating the input signal with sinusoids, which a neural network can achieve by setting the output node weights to match the desired sinusoidal patterns.

Given this, one might ask whether a network designed with traditional DSP strategies is optimal. Conventional DSP algorithms are based on assumptions about input signal

characteristics, such as *Wiener filtering*² assuming known signal and noise spectra, or correlation assuming white noise³. The issue is that in practice, scientists and engineers rarely have perfect knowledge of the input signals, which limits the performance of these mathematically elegant algorithms.

For instance, after testing a conventional DSP algorithm with real data, slightly tweaking one parameter might yield better results. This suggests that the original algorithm wasn't fully optimized for the task. Almost all DSP algorithms can be significantly improved through small, trial-and-error adjustments to parameters and processes—an approach similar to how neural networks optimize through learning.

Figure 2.5: Example image of text. Recognizing letters in images is a common task for neural networks nowadays. In this example, each letter is represented as a small 10x10 image, where each pixel has 256 shades of gray. A dataset with 50 samples of each of the 26 capital letters (totaling 1,300 images) was used to train and test the neural network. The displayed images are examples from this dataset. Reprinted from *The Scientist and Engineer's Guide to Digital Signal Processing* by Steven W. Smith, 1997, p. 466. Copyright 1997 by California Technical. [45]

2.3 Training the NN

Neural network design can best be explained with an example. Figure 2.5 shows the problem we will address: identifying individual letters in an image of text. This pattern recognition task has received much attention. It is easy enough that many approaches achieve partial success, but difficult enough that there are no perfect solutions. Many applications have been based on this problem, such as OCR programs.

²The **Wiener filter** is a filter used to produce an estimate of a desired or target random process by linear time-invariant (LTI) filtering of an observed noisy process, assuming known stationary signal and noise spectra, and additive noise. It's commonly used in applications like noise reduction and signal detection.

³**White noise** is a random signal having equal intensity at different frequencies

The first step in developing a neural network is to create a database of examples. For the text recognition problem, this is accomplished by printing the 26 capital letters ("A", "B", "C", ..., "Y", "Z") 50 times on a sheet of paper. Next, these 1300 letters are converted into a digital image by using one of the many scanning devices available for personal computers. This large digital image is then divided into small images of 10×10 pixels, each containing a single letter. This information is stored as a database: 1300 images; 100 pixels per image; 8 bits per pixel. We will use the first 260 images in this database to train the neural network (i.e., determine the weights), and the remainder to test its performance. The database must also contain a way of identifying the letter contained in each image. For instance, an additional byte could be added to each 10×10 image, containing the letter's ASCII code. In another scheme, the position of each 10×10 picture in the database could indicate what the letter is.

For this demonstration, the neural network will be designed for an arbitrary task: determine which of the 10×10 images contains a vowel ("A", "E", "I", "O", or "U"). This illustrates the ability of the neural network to learn very abstract pattern recognition problems. By including ten examples of each letter in the training set, the network will learn the key features that distinguish the target (vowel) from the non-target images. The neural network used in this example is the traditional three-layer, fully interconnected architecture. There are 101 nodes in the input layer (100 pixel values plus a bias node), 10 nodes in the hidden layer, and 1 node in the output layer. When a 100-pixel image is applied to the input of the network, we want the output value to be close to one if a vowel is present, and near zero if a vowel is not present. It's not important that the input signal was acquired as a two-dimensional array (10×10), while the input to the neural network is a one-dimensional array. This is your understanding of how the pixel values are interrelated; the neural network will find relationships of its own.

Subsection 2.3.1 shows the main program for calculating the neural network weights, containing three subroutines called from the main program. The array elements $X1[1]$ through $X1[100]$ hold the input layer values. In addition, $X1[101]$ always holds a value of 1, providing the input to the bias node. The output values from the hidden nodes are contained in the array elements $X2[1]$ through $X2[10]$. The variable $X3$ contains the network's output value. The weights of the hidden layer are contained in the array $WH[,]$, where the first index identifies the hidden node (1 to 10), and the second index is the input layer node (1 to 101). The weights of the output layer are held in $WO[1]$ to $WO[10]$. This makes a total of 1020 weight values that define how the network will operate.

The first action of the program is to set each weight to an arbitrary initial value by using a random number generator. As shown in lines 19 to 24, the hidden layer weights are assigned initial values between -0.0005 and 0.0005, while the output layer weights

are between -0.5 and 0.5. These ranges are chosen to be the same order of magnitude as the final weights must be. This is based on:

1. the range of values in the input signal;
2. the number of inputs summed at each node;
3. the range of values over which the *sigmoid* is active, an input of about $-5 < x < 5$, and an output of 0 to 1.

For instance, when 101 inputs with a typical value of 100 are multiplied by the typical weight value of 0.0002, the sum of the products is about 2, which is in the active range of the *sigmoid*'s input. If we evaluated the performance of the neural network using these random weights, we would expect it to be the same as random guessing. The learning algorithm improves the performance of the network by gradually changing each weight in the proper direction. This is called an iterative procedure, and is controlled in the program by the *FOR-NEXT* loop in lines 270-400. Each iteration makes the weights slightly more efficient at separating the target from the non-target examples. The iteration loop is usually carried out until no further improvement is being made. In typical neural networks, this may be anywhere from ten to ten-thousand iterations, but a few hundred is common. This example carries out 800 iterations.

In order for this iterative strategy to work, there must be a single parameter that describes how well the system is currently performing. The variable *ESUM* (for *error sum*) serves this function in the program. The first action inside the iteration loop is to set *ESUM* to zero (line 29) so that it can be used as an accumulator. At the end of each iteration, the value of *ESUM* is printed to the video screen (line 38), so that the operator can ensure that progress is being made. The value of *ESUM* will start high, and gradually decrease as the neural network is trained to recognize the targets.

All 260 images in the training set are evaluated during each iteration, as controlled by the *FOR-NEXT* loop in lines 31-36. 2.3.1 is used to retrieve images from the database of examples. Since this is not something of particular interest here, we will only describe the parameters passed to and from this subroutine. 2.3.1 is entered with the parameter, *LETTER%*, being between 1 and 260. Upon return, the input node values, *X1[1]* to *X1[100]*, contain the pixel values for the image in the database corresponding to *LETTER%*. The bias node value, *X1[101]*, is always returned with a constant value of one. Subroutine 1000 also returns another parameter, *CORRECT*. This contains the desired output value of the network for this particular letter. That is, if the letter in the image is a vowel, *CORRECT* will be returned with a value of one. If the letter in the image is not a vowel, *CORRECT* will be returned with a value of zero.

After the image being worked on is loaded into *X1[1]* through *X1[100]*, 2.3.1 passes the data through the current neural network to produce the output node value, *X3*.

This subroutine also calculates how well the current network identifies the letter as a target or a non-target. In line 221, the variable *ELET* (for *error-letter*) is calculated as the difference between the output value actually generated, *X3*, and the desired value, *CORRECT*. This makes *ELET* a value between -1 and 1. All of the 260 values for *ELET* are combined (line 34) to form *ESUM*, the total squared error of the network for the entire training set.

Line 222 shows an option that is often included when calculating the error: assigning a different importance to the errors for targets and non-targets. For example, recall the cancer example presented earlier in this chapter, and the consequences of making a false-positive error versus a false-negative error. In the present example, we will arbitrarily declare that the error in detecting a target is five times as bad as the error in detecting a non-target. In effect, this tells the network to do a better job with the targets, even if it hurts the performance of the non-targets.

Subsection 2.3.1 is the heart of the neural network strategy, the algorithm for changing the weights on each iteration. In machine learning, the general goal is indeed to optimize the performance of a model, which typically involves adjusting the model's parameters (such as weights in a neural network) to minimize a *loss function*. A **loss function** quantifies how well the model's predictions match the actual values (the ground truth). By minimizing this function, we improve the model's accuracy or generalization ability. The process of adjusting the parameters of the model to minimize the loss is achieved through an *optimizer*.

An **optimizer** is an algorithm that iteratively adjusts the model's parameters in such a way that the value of the *loss function* decreases over time. The most common optimization techniques rely on the calculation of gradients, which indicate the direction of the steepest increase or decrease in the loss. Gradient-based methods like **Gradient Descent** are commonly used, where the parameters are adjusted in the opposite direction of the gradient to minimize the loss. In this section, we will discuss a special case of this algorithm called **Steepest Descent**. Other commonly used *loss functions* and *optimizer* are discussed in Appendix A. Here we will use an analogy to understand the process of adjusting the weights in a neural network during training. In the context of a neural network, the aim is to minimize the *ESUM* error function, which represent our *loss function*.

Now, let's explore the idea of **Steepest Descent** through an analogy. Imagine a military paratrooper dropped behind enemy lines. He parachutes to the ground in an unfamiliar territory and finds that it is so dark he can only see a few feet in front of him. His mission is to reach the bottom of the nearest valley, but without being able to see, how can he navigate towards the valley floor? This scenario mirrors the task of adjusting the weights in a neural network to minimize his elevation (or the network's

error), which is analogous to the paratrooper's goal of reaching the valley floor. Let's consider two algorithms that could help him: **Evolution** and **Steepest Descent**.

In **Evolution**, the paratrooper jumps in a random direction. If the new elevation is higher than the previous one, he returns to his starting point and tries again. If the new elevation is lower, he moves to that position and repeats the jumping process. This approach is completely arbitrary and does not know which direction is downhill. While powerful for exploring large knowledge bases, evolution is very inefficient, and it would take the paratrooper several lifetimes to find the valley floor.

On the other hand, **Steepest Descent** allows the paratrooper (representing the optimizer) to take small steps and measure the slope of the ground in each direction. This helps him move directly downhill in the steepest direction, continually reassessing the slope as he proceeds toward the valley floor. Unlike *Evolution*, *Steepest Descent* is efficient because it makes informed adjustments, but it requires that the slope be measurable at each position. This method is widely used to train neural networks, and it is the technique implemented in this chapter.

To understand the mathematics behind steepest descent, let's consider the example of changing one of the hidden layer weights, say $WH[5, 20]$, which connects the twentieth input to the fifth hidden node. Initially, this weight starts with a small arbitrary value, $WH^{(\text{old})}[5, 20]$. After passing the 260 training letters through the network, we compute the current error value, $ESUM$. Now, suppose we make a small change in this weight, $WH^{(\text{new})}[5, 20] = WH^{(\text{old})}[5, 20] + \Delta W$. We then pass the training data again, resulting in a new value of $ESUM$. The slope of $ESUM$ with respect to $WH[5, 20]$ is given by:

$$S = \frac{ESUM^{(\text{new})} - ESUM^{(\text{old})}}{\Delta W} \quad (2.3)$$

The objective is to adjust the weight in the direction that minimizes $ESUM$. To do this, we subtract a term proportional to the slope:

$$WH^{(\text{new})}[5, 20] = WH^{(\text{old})}[5, 20] - K \cdot S \quad (2.4)$$

Here, K is a positive constant that ensures the changes are small enough to maintain the validity of the slope. If K is too small, the network will require many iterations to converge. If K is too large, the network might become unstable and fail to converge to an optimal solution.

The key challenge in steepest descent is calculating the slope S , which represents the **gradient** of $ESUM$ with respect to each weight. Instead of making small changes and recalculating the network error, we can directly compute the slope using the chain rule from calculus, without modifying the weights. Since the sigmoid function is continuous and differentiable, this process is computationally efficient. This is one of the reasons the

sigmoid function is commonly used in neural networks: it facilitates efficient calculation of the gradient.

Section 2.3.1 details the equations used to calculate the slopes. For example, line 316 calculates the slope for the output layer weights, while lines 305-312 handle the hidden layer weights. To illustrate, let's look at the specific case of adjusting the first output layer weight, $WO[1]$. We want to compute the gradient:

$$\frac{\partial ESUM}{\partial WO[1]} \quad (2.5)$$

Using the chain rule of calculus, this can be expressed as:

$$\frac{\partial ESUM}{\partial WO[1]} = \sum_k \left(\frac{\partial ESUM}{\partial ELET[k]} \cdot \frac{\partial ELET[k]}{\partial X3[k]} \cdot \frac{\partial X3[k]}{\partial WO[1]} \right) \quad (2.6)$$

The sum is over all 260 training examples (indexed by k), where each example produces an output value $X3[k]$ and an error value $ELET[k]$. The partial derivatives in this expression can be evaluated as follows: 1. The derivative of $ESUM$ with respect to each $ELET$ is:

$$ESUM = ESUM + ELET^2 \quad \Rightarrow \quad \frac{\partial ESUM}{\partial ELET} = 2 \cdot ELET \quad (2.7)$$

2. The derivative of each $ELET$ with respect to $X3[k]$ is:

$$ELET[k] = X3[k] - CORRECT[k] \quad \Rightarrow \quad \frac{\partial ELET[k]}{\partial X3[k]} = 1 \quad (2.8)$$

3. The derivative of each output node value with respect to the weight is:

$$X3[k] = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-NET3)} \quad \Rightarrow \quad \frac{\partial X3[k]}{\partial NET3} = X3[k] \cdot (1 - X3[k]) \quad (2.9)$$

Finally, $NET3$ represents the total input to the output node, which is:

$$NET3 = \sum_i (WO[i] \cdot X2[i]) \quad \Rightarrow \quad \frac{\partial NET3}{\partial WO[1]} = X2[1] \quad (2.10)$$

By combining these results, the gradient of $ESUM$ with respect to $WO[1]$ is:

$$\frac{\partial ESUM}{\partial WO[1]} = \sum_k (2 \cdot ELET[k] \cdot 1 \cdot X3[k] \cdot (1 - X3[k]) \cdot X2[1]) \quad (2.11)$$

The calculation for other weights, such as $WO[2]$ through $WO[10]$, follows the same logic. The procedure for adjusting the hidden layer weights is similar but involves a slightly more complex chain rule.

2.3.1 Pseudocode

Finding weights

```

10 'NEURAL NETWORK TRAINING (Determination of weights)
11 '
12             'INITIALIZE
13 MU = .000005 'iteration step size
14 DIM X1[101]  'holds the input layer signal + bias term
15 DIM X2[10]   'holds the hidden layer signal
16 DIM WH[10,101] 'holds hidden layer weights
17 DIM WO[10]   'holds output layer weights
18 '
19 FOR H% = 1 TO 10             'SET WEIGHTS TO RANDOM VALUES
20     WO[H%] = (RND-0.5) 'output layer weights: -0.5 to 0.5
21     FOR I% = 1 TO 101 'hidden layer weights: -0.0005 to 0.0005
22         WH[H%,I%] = (RND-0.5)/1000
23     NEXT I%
24 NEXT H%
25 '
26 '             'ITERATION LOOP
27 FOR ITER% = 1 TO 800 'loop for 800 iterations
28 '
29 ESUM = 0 'clear the error accumulator, ESUM
30 '
31 FOR LETTER% = 1 TO 260 'loop for each letter in the training set
32 GOSUB 1000 'load X1[ ] with training set
33 GOSUB 2000 'find the error for this letter, ELET
34 ESUM = ESUM + ELET^2 'accumulate error for this iteration
35 GOSUB 3000 'find the new weights
36 NEXT LETTER%
37 '
38 PRINT ITER% ESUM 'print the progress to the video screen
39 '
40 NEXT ITER%
41 '
42 GOSUB XXXX 'mythical subroutine to save the weights
43 END

```

Loading images

```

100 'SUBROUTINE TO LOAD X1[ ] WITH IMAGES FROM THE DATABASE

```

```

101 'Variables entering routine: LETTER%
102 'Variables exiting routine: X1[1] to X1[100], X1[101] = 1, CORRECT
103 '
104 'The variable, LETTER%, between 1 and 260,
      indicates which image in the database is to be
105 'returned in X1[1] to X1[100]. The bias node,
      X1[101], always has a value of one. The variable,
106 'CORRECT, has a value of one if the image being
      returned is a vowel, and zero otherwise.
107 '(The details of this subroutine are unimportant, and
      not listed here).
190 RETURN

```

Calculating errors

```

200 'SUBROUTINE TO CALCULATE THE ERROR WITH THE CURRENT WEIGHTS
201 'Variables entering routine: X1[ ], X2[ ], WI[ ], WH[ ], CORRECT
202 'Variables exiting routine: ELET
203 '
204 '          'FIND THE HIDDEN NODE VALUES, X2[ ]
205 FOR H% = 1 TO 10  'loop for each hidden nodes
206   ACC = 0          'clear the accumulator
207   FOR I% = 1 TO 101  'weight and sum each input node
208     ACC = ACC + X1[I%] * WH[H%,I%]
209   NEXT I%
210   X2[H%] = 1 / (1 + EXP(-ACC) ) 'pass summed value
                                   through sigmoid
211 NEXT H%
212 '
213 '          'FIND THE OUTPUT VALUE: X3
214 ACC = 0          'clear the accumulator
215 FOR H% = 1 TO 10  'weight and sum each hidden node
216 ACC = ACC + X2[H%] * WO[H%]
217 NEXT H%
218 X3 = 1 / (1 + EXP(-ACC) )          'pass summed value through sigmoid
219 '
220 '          'FIND ERROR FOR THIS LETTER, ELET
221 ELET = (CORRECT - X3)              'find the error
222 IF CORRECT = 1 THEN ELET = ELET*5 'give extra weight to targets
223 '
224 RETURN

```

Finding new weights

```

300 'SUBROUTINE TO FIND NEW WEIGHTS
301 'Variables entering routine: X1[ ], X2[ ], X3, WI[ , ], WH[ ],
           ELET, MU
302 'Variables exiting routine: WI[ , ], WH[ ]
303 '
304 '           'FIND NEW WEIGHTS FOR HIDDEN LAYER
305 FOR H% = 1 TO 10
306 FOR I% = 1 TO 101
307 SLOPEO = X3 * (1 - X3)
308 SLOPEH = X2(H%) * (1 - X2[H%])
309 DX3DW = X1[I%] * SLOPEH * WO[H%] * SLOPEO
310 WH[H%,I%] = WH[H%,I%] + DX3DW * ELET * MU
311 NEXT I%
312 NEXT H%
313 '
314 '           'FIND NEW WEIGHTS FOR OUTPUT LAYER
315 FOR H% = 1 TO 10
316 SLOPEO = X3 * (1 - X3)
317 DX3DW = X2[H%] * SLOPEO
318 WO[H%] = WO[H%] + DX3DW * ELET * MU
319 NEXT H%
320 '
321 RETURN

```

2.4 Evaluate the NN

2.4.1 Training and Performance of Neural Networks for Vowel Recognition

The training program for vowel recognition was executed three times, each time using different random values for the initial weights. Figure 2.6 illustrates how the network error, *ESUM*, evolves over this period. The gradual decline in *ESUM* indicates that the network is effectively learning the task, and that the weights approach near-optimal values after several hundred iterations. Each trial yields a distinct solution to the problem, resulting in varied final performance levels. This variation is akin to a paratrooper starting from different locations and hence reaching the bottom of different valleys. Just as some valleys are deeper than others, some neural network solutions are superior. Consequently, it is recommended to run the learning algorithm multiple times and

select the best outcome as the final solution.

Figure 2.6: This graph tracks how the *loss function* (*ESUM*) in the neural network decreases as it goes through multiple iterations of learning. It shows results from three trials, each starting with different initial settings. Over time, the network improves, reducing the error. Reprinted from *The Scientist and Engineer's Guide to Digital Signal Processing* by Steven W. Smith, 1997, p. 471. Copyright 1997 by California Technical. [45]

In Figure 2.7 the hidden layer weights of the three solutions are displayed as images. This means that the initial action performed by the neural network is to correlate (multiply and sum) these images with the input signal. These weight values appear as random noise! Although they can be shown to work, the reason behind their effectiveness remains a mystery.

Figure 2.8a presents a histogram of the neural network's output for the 260 letters in the training set. Recall that the weights were chosen to make the output close to one for vowel images and near zero for others. The separation is perfect, with no overlap between the two distributions. Additionally, the vowel distribution is narrower than the nonvowel distribution. This is because we assigned the target error to be five times more important than the nontarget error (refer to line 2220). In contrast, 2.8b shows the histogram for images 261 through 1300 in the database. Here, the target and nontarget distributions are reasonably distinct but not completely separated. Why does the neural network perform better on the first 260 letters than the last 1040? 2.8a represents a case of "cheating": it's easy to excel on a test if you have already seen the answers. In other words, the neural network is recognizing specific images in the training set rather than the general patterns distinguishing vowels from non-vowels.

Figure 2.7: This figure visualizes the weights in the hidden layer of the network for three different solutions. Reprinted from *The Scientist and Engineer's Guide to Digital Signal Processing* by Steven W. Smith, 1997, p. 474. Copyright 1997 by California Technical. [45]

Figure 2.9 depicts the performance of the three solutions as ROC curves. Trial (b) yields a significantly better network compared to the other two. This is a result of random chance associated with the initial weights. At a specific threshold setting, the neural network designed in trial (b) can detect 24 out of 25 targets (i.e., 96% of the vowel images) with a false alarm rate of only 1 in 25 non-targets (i.e., 4% of the nonvowel images).

Figure 2.8: These graphs show how well the neural network performs. One graph shows the network's output for the data it was trained on, and the other for new data it hasn't seen before. The network performs better on the training data because it already "knows" the correct answers. Reprinted from *The Scientist and Engineer's Guide to Digital Signal Processing* by Steven W. Smith, 1997, p. 475. Copyright 1997 by California Technical. [45]

Figure 2.9: ROC curve of neural network examples. This analysis compares three neural networks designed to detect vowel images. The best-performing network is shown by a curve that is closest to the top-left corner of the graph. This network correctly identifies 96% of vowel images while making only 4% false detections. Reprinted from *The Scientist and Engineer's Guide to Digital Signal Processing* by Steven W. Smith, 1997, p. 475. Copyright 1997 by California Technical. [45]

2.4.2 Considerations and Recommendations

Achieving convergence during neural network training can be challenging. If the network error (like *ESUM*) does not consistently decrease, the training process must be terminated, adjusted, and restarted. This may require several attempts before success is achieved. There are three key factors that can be modified to influence convergence:

1. **MU (learning rate):** Adjusting this parameter can help in finding the optimal weight adjustments during training.
2. **Magnitude of the initial random weights:** Properly setting the range of initial weights can ensure the network starts training within a suitable scope.
3. **Number of hidden nodes:** The architecture of the neural network, including the number of hidden nodes, plays a crucial role in its ability to learn and generalize from the training data.

The most crucial aspect of neural network development is the validity of the training examples. In the context of commercial product development, the available test data often come from prototypes, simulations, or educated guesses. Training a neural network on this preliminary data might lead to suboptimal performance in the final application. Any discrepancies between the training database and the eventual real-world data will

degrade the neural network's performance.

2.5 Brief history of NN

The concept of neural networks dates back to the early work of Warren McCulloch and Walter Pitts in the 1940s, in which they discuss how neurons might work and modeled a simple network using electric circuit. In 1958, Frank Rosenblatt introduced the **perceptron**, an early form of a neural network designed for pattern recognition. However, this initial excitement was short-lived due to the perceptron's limitations, notably its inability to solve non-linear problems, as shown in 1969 by Marvin Minsky and Seymour Papert in their 1969 book, *Perceptrons. An Introduction to Computational Geometry*. This led to reduced interest in neural networks for several years. Despite this, researchers like Paul Werbos and others continued developing the backpropagation algorithm in the 1970s, which would become crucial later for training deeper networks. In 1969, Kunihiro Fukushima introduced the *ReLU* (*rectified linear unit*) activation function, the most popular activation function for deep learning (presented in A.3.1. In 1979 Fukushima also introduced the first architecture of *convolutional neural network* with *max pooling*, a popular downsampling procedure for CNNs (explained in 3.2.3. CNNs, which are discussed in Chapter 3, have become an essential tool for computer vision.

In 1982, John Hopfield introduced *Hopfield networks*, a type of *recurrent neural network* that could store and retrieve memories based on collective processing, akin to human associative memory. His work demonstrated that neural networks could act as energy minimization systems, with applications to pattern recognition and optimization problems. Hopfield's model, which could solve problems by evolving to stable states (*local minima*), became one of the most influential ideas in neural computation, bridging the gap between physics and neural network theory. His networks have since been applied to various problems in optimization and machine learning and led to a major interest in NNs in the last decades.

At the same time, Geoffrey Hinton, David Rumelhart, and others were exploring ways to make multi-layer networks more powerful. Their work in the 1980s led to the development of the *backpropagation algorithm*, which allowed neural networks to adjust their internal weights through multiple layers. This breakthrough enabled the training of what we now call deep neural networks, allowing machines to learn complex patterns and make sophisticated decisions.

While the theoretical basis for neural networks was solidifying, practical applications were still limited due to computational constraints. During the 1990s and early 2000s, advances in computing hardware, especially the rise of *graphical processing units* (*GPUs*),

made it possible to train larger neural networks. In 1989, Yann LeCun et al. created a CNN called *LeNet* for recognizing handwritten ZIP codes on mail (3.4.1). Training required 3 days. In 1991, a CNN was applied to medical image object segmentation and breast cancer detection in mammograms. These breakthroughs showed the potential for neural networks to revolutionize fields beyond computer science, from healthcare to autonomous systems.

By the 2010s, neural networks—particularly deep learning—had become central to the AI revolution. This period saw a surge in practical applications of neural networks, thanks to large datasets and unprecedented computational power. Geoffrey Hinton with his students Alex Krizhevsky and Ilya Sutskever won the 2012 *ImageNet* competition with *AlexNet* (3.4.2), a pivotal moment that demonstrated the power of these models in image classification tasks. The synergy between neural networks and scientific research was further demonstrated by *AlphaFold*, a deep learning model developed by DeepMind. In 2020, *AlphaFold* solved one of biology’s grand challenges: predicting protein structures from amino acid sequences. This breakthrough had immense implications for fields ranging from drug discovery to genetic research. For their contribution, Demis Hassabis and John M. Jumper from Deepmind were awarded with 2024 Nobel Prize in Chemistry, together with David Baker.

In 2017, the **Transformer** network enabled advancements in generative models, leading to the first *generative pre-trained transformer (GPT)*, known as *GPT-1*, developed by *OpenAI* in 2018. *Transformer* models allowed AI to understand context and generate coherent, human-like text across a range of applications. This innovation led to major advances in areas such as machine translation, chatbots, and content creation. In 2024, Geoffrey Hinton and John Hopfield were awarded the Nobel Prize in Physics for their pioneering work on neural networks and contributions to understanding complex systems in both artificial intelligence and biological neural networks.

2.6 NNs classification

In this section some types of neural networks will be briefly discussed.

- **Feedforward Neural Networks (FNNs)**

The most basic type of neural network, also known as a **Multilayer Perceptron (MLP)**. Information moves in one direction—from input to output—without loops or cycles.

- **Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs)**

CNNs will be discussed in Chapter 3. They are designed for processing grid-like

data such as images. CNNs use *convolutional layers* to automatically extract features from input data. They are mainly used in image classification, video processing and medical science.

- **Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs)**

A type of network where connections between nodes form directed cycles, allowing them to maintain a memory of previous inputs. RNNs are designed to handle sequential data by processing one element at a time while preserving information from previous elements. They are useful in *natural language processing* (NLP), speech recognition and video analysis.

- **Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs)**

A class of neural networks composed of *two models*—a *generator* that produces new data instances, and a *discriminator* that evaluates the authenticity of the generated data. The two models compete in a game, improving over time. They are often use in image generation and realistic simulations.

- **Autoencoders**

Networks designed to compress data into a lower-dimensional representation (*encoding*) and then reconstruct the data back to its original form (*decoding*). They are used for unsupervised learning and data dimensionality reduction.

- **Transformers**

A type of neural network architecture that uses attention mechanisms to weigh the importance of different input elements dynamically. Unlike RNNs, *Transformers* process all input data in parallel, making them highly efficient for handling large-scale sequential data. For these reasons, they are used in NLP tasks and LLMs.

- **Radial Basis Function Networks (RBFNs)**

A neural network that uses *radial basis* functions as *activation functions*. RBFNs are typically used for pattern recognition, interpolation, and time-series prediction

- **Self-Organizing Maps (SOMs)**

An unsupervised learning algorithm that uses competitive learning to produce a low-dimensional, discretized representation of input space, preserving the topological properties of the input data.

- **Modular Neural Networks (MNNs)**

These are networks consisting of several independent networks (*modules*) that each perform sub-tasks. The results of the *modules* are combined to produce the final output (e.g. in robotics).

- **Echo State Networks (ESNs)**

A type of recurrent neural network designed with a sparse random network, where only the output layer is trained, while the internal connections remain fixed.

- **Capsule Networks (CapsNets)**

Designed to address some of the shortcomings of CNNs, particularly when it comes to recognizing spatial hierarchies in data. Capsule networks are more resistant to spatial transformations (e.g., rotations or scaling).

- **Spiking Neural Networks (SNNs)**

A type of biologically inspired neural network that more closely mimics the way real neurons communicate using *spikes* (discrete events in time) rather than continuous activations.

- **Recursive Neural Networks (RecNNs)**

These networks are a generalization of RNNs, where instead of processing sequential data, they process hierarchical data structures like *parse trees*. This makes them useful for tasks where input has a recursive structure.

- **Liquid Neural Networks**

A new type of neural network inspired by liquid brain matter, in which the architecture adapts its connections over time, allowing it to generalize better to unseen tasks (e.g. self-driving cars).

Convolutional Neural Networks

In this chapter we present the main features of *Convolutional Neural Networks* and some notable examples of architecture. For a more detailed discussion, please refer to *Convolutional Neural Networks in Visual Computing: A Concise Guide*[11].

3.1 Introduction to CNNs

In the previous chapter, we introduced a *multi-layer neural network* (MLNN). While an MLNN can be effective in some scenarios, including simple image recognition, we may need a more targeted method for analyzing astronomical images. In this chapter, we will explore a specific type of neural network, called **Convolutional Neural Networks** (CNNs), which are particularly useful for capturing local dependencies among features through the use of convolutional and pooling layers[12].

3.2 Convolution and Pooling Layers

3.2.1 Convolution Operation

Imagine a neural network where connections between neurons are *sparse*¹. This sparsity is applied randomly, and only some adjacent connections are kept active (we assume $k = 3$ for adjacency here). In this configuration, each neuron learns a local property of the input, as it only processes three neighboring features. The goal is to capture how features vary locally. These connections are considered local when linked to adjacent dimensions of the signal. For images, this means neighboring pixels, where the pixel arrangement corresponds to the image structure.

If each neuron is connected to a local subset of inputs and the weights are treated as a kernel, this kernel only applies locally. However, for images, we often want to

¹**Sparsity** refers to situations in which a significant number of the elements in a dataset, matrix, or model parameters are zero or have no significant value. Having a sparse set of weights implies that most of the weights will be absolute zero

detect patterns across the entire signal. Therefore, instead of restricting the neuron to a specific local area, we allow it to move or "slide" across the entire input, maintaining its adjacency but shifting to other regions as well. This way, the neuron can gather information from different parts of the signal. This sliding mechanism increases the number of outputs without increasing the number of weights. The outputs are structured in a way that they approximately match the size of the original input.

Now, consider a d -dimensional feature vector $\mathbf{x} = [x^{(1)}, x^{(2)}, \dots, x^{(d)}]$ as input to a layer. With a fixed set of weights $\omega = [\omega_1, \omega_2, \dots, \omega_k]$, we start at the beginning of the input and slide the weights across the input with a stride of one feature at a time. This gathers the neuron's response at each position. Mathematically, this operation is described as:

$$z^{(j)} = \sum_{i=1}^k x^{(j+i-1)} \omega_k, \quad \forall j = [1, 2, \dots, d - k + 1] \quad (3.1)$$

This is commonly referred to as **convolution**, though a more precise term might be *cross-correlation*. While true convolution involves flipping the kernel, we often refer to both operations as convolution interchangeably. This is an example of 1D convolution, where the outputs of the neurons $z^{(j)}$ share the same weights and produce an output of length $d - k + 1$.

The neural responses can then be passed through *activation functions* such as *ReLU* (*Rectified Linear Unit*) (Subsection A.3.1), resulting in what we call **feature maps** or **activations**. The number of *feature maps* corresponds to the number of filters (shared-weight neurons) in the network. These filters are also known as **kernels**. Since each filter captures signals from adjacent input features, its receptive field is of size k , covering specific local regions in the input.

The debate over the size of receptive fields continues: one viewpoint favors smaller filters (around 3 pixels), while another suggests starting with larger filters and reducing the size in deeper layers.

3.2.2 2D Convolution

A 2D convolutional layer functions similarly to a 1D convolutional layer, except that the *filters* are organized in two dimensions. Each neuron moves across the input from one corner of the image to the opposite corner. In this case, the input consists of multiple *channels* or *feature maps*, such as the different color channels of an image.

Consider the input layer \mathbf{a} with I channels and a layer with L kernels \mathbf{k} , along with the *activation function* λ . The output of the layer is computed as:

$$z^j = \lambda \left(\sum_{i=1}^I a^{(i)} * k_j \right), \quad \forall j = [1, 2, \dots, L] \quad (3.2)$$

Here, $*$ represents convolution (3.1). The key difference in CNNs is that the filters are learned by the network. CNNs decompose images into fundamental components like edges or blobs, especially in the first layer. Deeper layers combine these simple components into more complex representations.

Figure 3.1: Step-by-step illustration of the convolution operation in a single-channel padded image. The term *padding* refers to the common addition of extra values (typically zeros) around the edges of an image or matrix. It is used to preserve the dimensions of the input image and ensure the filter can process edge regions effectively. The padded image (left) is a 6×6 matrix with zero-padding (padding size = 1). A 3×3 filter (middle) is applied to compute the output *feature map* (right), resulting in a 6×6 matrix. The calculation for a single output value (7) is shown below, demonstrating element-wise multiplication between a 3×3 region of the padded image and the filter, followed by summation.[46].

3.2.3 Pooling

In *convolutional layers*, nearby neurons often detect similar features due to the smooth transitions in the input. As a result, the *convolutional filters* are relatively small, but they scan large areas of the image. To enhance learning by capturing sharper transitions, a process called **pooling** usually follows the *convolutional layer*. *Pooling* reduces the spatial resolution of the activations, simplifying the data while preserving important information.

Pooling reduces *entropy* (Subsection A.1.2) by shrinking the size of activations, which increases the response density at the cost of some spatial and frequency details. Most importantly, *pooling* introduces spatial invariance, making the network more robust

while reducing computational complexity.

In CNNs, **max pooling** is the most common method. It works by selecting the maximum value within a sliding window of size $p \times p$, with a stride equal to the window size. *Max pooling* is generally preferred because it captures the strongest activations, helping to highlight the most important features (Figure 3.2).

Figure 3.2: Comparison between *max pooling* and *average pooling*. The first takes the maximum value from the portion of the input *feature map* covered by the kernel while the second compute the average of all values in the portion covered by the kernel[47].

3.3 Fully connected layers

A **fully connected layer (FC)** is a layer where every neuron of the previous layer is connected to every neuron of current layer. These layers are typically found toward the end of a neural network, especially in CNNs, where they are used to interpret the high-level features detected by previous layers and make final decisions or classifications.

In CNNs, FC are used to flatten the 2D spatial structure of the data into a 1D vector and process this data for tasks like classification. The number of neurons in the final FC layer usually matches the number of output classes in a classification problem. For instance, for a 10-class classification problem, there would be 10 neurons in the final FC layer, each outputting a score for one of the classes[13].

3.4 Notable CNNs architectures

3.4.1 LeNet

LeNet (Figure 3.3) is one of the most popular CNNs. It was developed by Yan LeCun for digit recognition in 1998[14]. This architecture is also referred as **LeNet5** and has two *convolutional layers* and one *fully connected layer*. The number of *feature maps* in the first layer is usually 20 in modern interactions.

Figure 3.3: The architecture of LeNet-5[48].

3.4.2 AlexNet

This CNN was the winner of the ImageNet challenge in 2012 and was developed by the team of Geoffrey Hinton, Nobel laureate in 2024[15]. At the time, *ImageNet* was a dataset with over 15 million images divided in 22000 categories. The competition used about 1000 of these. Many categories are very complicated to identify: human performance in this test is about 96%. *AlexNet*, as we saw in Section 2.5, was the first ANN to break the mark of 80%.

AlexNet is essentially a deeper *LeNet*. It has five *convolutional layer blocks* (each made up by *convolutional* and *pooling layers*) followed by two *fully connected layers*. At the time, was one of the most largest and deepest neural network. It's one of the first CNN to implement *ReLU* as *activation function*, which helped to increase speed. Another contribution was the use of more GPUs for learning, which now is standard.

AlexNet also introduced **dropouts**, a method to avoid coadaptation of feature maps. In *dropouts* the output of a neuron is forced to zero with random probability. Approximately half of the neurons in the network typically turn-off randomly while learning. So each neuron is now under the stress to learn meaningful feature, avoiding *overfitting*². Neuron also cannot coadapt and must learn feature independently from each others. During *dropout*, effectively a new network is created. These models now share parameters.

²**Overfitting** is a typical phenomenon in machine learning where a neural network learns the training data too precisely, including its noise and random fluctuations, instead of learning the underlying general pattern. This results in a model that performs exceptionally well on training data but fails to generalize effectively to new, unseen data.

3.4.3 VGG

The **VGG** architecture was introduced by Karen Simonyan and Andrew Zisserman in 2014[16]. In the previous architecture, filters are larger at earlier layers and smaller in size at deeper layers. In VGG the first receptive field starts as small as 3×3 and grows at constant pace of 3×3 . The most common architecture version is *VGG-19*³, also known as *VGGNet* or *VGG-E* (as called in the original paper).

³19 refers to the number of layers in the network

Part II

Development

Introduction to PyTorch

In this chapter, we will mainly present PyTorch, the machine learning library used in this work, alongside a simple example of a CNN.

4.1 PyTorch

PyTorch is an open-source machine learning library, originally developed by *Facebook's Artificial Intelligence Research division* (now *Meta AI*). Since September 2022, *PyTorch* has been governed by the independent *PyTorch Foundation*, a subsidiary of the *Linux Foundation*[17]. PyTorch easily runs array-based calculations, builds dynamic neural networks, and performs auto-differentiation with strong GPU¹ acceleration[19]. *PyTorch* provides interfaces for both C++ and Python, but the latter is the main focus of development. **Python** is a high-level, portable, interpreted programming language and object-oriented. Thanks to its simplicity, elegance, modernity, integration, and extensibility, it is an ideal candidate for scientific applications such as data analysis, simulations, graphing, and algebraic manipulation[20].

PyTorch is historically the most used library in research. It uses dynamic computation graphs (also called *define-by-run*), allowing users to define and modify models on the fly. It integrates seamlessly with other Python libraries, such as *NumPy*, making it easier to experiment and prototype. Its tools for production, such as *TorchScript*, allow researchers to transition their models into deployment-ready systems easily. This dual-purpose design has made it more appealing than earlier frameworks like *TensorFlow*, which focuses more on production use cases.

¹A **graphics processing unit (GPU)** is a specialized electronic circuit initially designed for digital image processing and to accelerate computer graphics[18]. In recent years, GPUs have been increasingly used for parallel calculations, such as training neural networks on enormous datasets required for large language models, instead of CPUs. The latest GPUs have specifically designed cores for deep learning, called tensor cores, available in both consumer and professional products.

4.2 Main PyTorch Modules and Classes

4.2.1 Tensors

PyTorch defines a class called **Tensor** (`torch.Tensor`) to store and operate on homogeneous multidimensional rectangular arrays of numbers, similar to *NumPy* arrays, with the key addition being that *tensors* can also be used on a GPU. *PyTorch* defines seven CPU tensor types and eight GPU tensor types for different purposes[21].

4.2.2 Autograd

Autograd is PyTorch's module that provides functionality for automatic differentiation of tensors. A recorder class in the program remembers the operations and retrieves those operations with a trigger called *backward* to compute the gradients. Using *Autograd*, *PyTorch* keeps track of all operations applied to tensors that have the `requires_grad` flag enabled, constructing a computation graph where each node represents a tensor, and the edges represent operations. During the backward pass, *Autograd* traverses the computational graph in reverse (from output to input) and computes gradients using the chain rule of calculus[21].

4.2.3 Optim

The **Optim** module[22] provides optimization techniques that can be used to minimize the error function for a specific model. These algorithms adjust the parameters of a model (e.g., *weights* and *biases*) to minimize the *loss function*, which measures the difference between the model's predictions and the true values[21].

Optimization algorithms (A.2) as seen in Section 2.3 are crucial in machine learning because they drive the learning process by updating the model parameters based on the computed gradients. Currently, *PyTorch* supports various advanced optimization methods. In particular, it includes **Adam** (short for *Adaptive Moment Estimation*), one of the most widely used optimization algorithms in Deep Learning (*Adam* is presented in A.2.5).

4.2.4 NN

`torch.nn` is the module that, as the name suggests, provides the tools to build and train neural network models. It contains layers, *activation functions*, *loss functions*, and utilities that make programming and training efficient and straightforward.

4.3 Python IDEs for ML Applications

For writing and executing code in *Python*, it is crucial to choose an IDE (*Integrated Development Environment*) with all the necessary features. In particular, for AI applications, strong support for data science libraries and GPUs is required. For this work, we opted for **PyCharm** and **Google Colab** for different phases and reasons.

PyCharm is a professional IDE developed by JetBrains. It provides advanced coding features and supports large-scale project organization. It also has powerful debugging tools that allow users to step through code and make changes on the fly. *PyCharm* makes it easy to configure and manage virtual environments (e.g., **Conda**, which was the one we used), ensuring dependency isolation and compatibility.

Google Colab is a cloud-based notebook environment provided by Google, very similar to *Jupyter Notebooks*, which is particularly advantageous for machine learning and data science tasks. It provides free access to GPUs and TPUs² (although with some limitations) to accelerate learning phases in the absence of local hardware. It also comes with pre-installed ML libraries, including *PyTorch*, reducing setup time.

As mentioned, both were used: *PyCharm* has been the main environment for development and production workflows, while *Google Colab* was sometimes used for cloud-based prototyping and experimentation.

4.4 Example of CNN Built Using PyTorch

As a toy example of a CNN developed using *PyTorch*, we present a simple image classifier. In this case, the *CIFAR-10* dataset has been used, an image collection made by Alex Krizhevsky, Vinod Nair, and Geoffrey Hinton. The *CIFAR-10* dataset consists of 60000 32x32 color images in 10 mutually-exclusive classes (*'airplane'*, *'automobile'*, *'bird'*, *'cat'*, *'deer'*, *'dog'*, *'frog'*, *'horse'*, *'ship'*, *'truck'*), with 6000 images per class. There are 50000 training images and 10000 test images[23]. The example is aimed to be used with *Jupyter-style Python notebooks*, such as *Google Colab*.

The first phase, as a good programming practice, requires importing the main libraries and defining functions. The `import` command allows us to load the libraries we need. Obviously, the first one is `torch`. Alongside the already presented `NN` and `Optim`, we will import `DataLoader` to load our data as training and testing sets. Other packages include `matplotlib` for graphing, `torchvision` to import *CIFAR-10* and modify our images to improve analysis, and `torchsummary` to display our NN structure while running the code.

²**Tensor Processing Units (TPUs)** are AI accelerators developed by Google for machine learning.

```
[1]: import torch
import torch.nn as nn
import torch.optim as optim
from torchvision import datasets, transforms
from torch.utils.data import DataLoader
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from torchsummary import summary
```

The CNN is defined as a class (`SimpleCNN`). The network consists of two *convolutional layers* (`conv1`, `conv2`) that apply a 3x3 filter to the input. The first *convolution maps* 3 input channels (RGB) to 16 *feature maps*, and the second layer maps 16 to 32 *feature maps*. A *pooling layer* (`pool`) performs 2x2 *max pooling*, which reduces the spatial dimensions by half. Two *fully connected layers* (`fc1`, `fc2`) follow the *convolutional layers* to perform classification. The first layer maps the flattened features to 128 units, and the second maps these to 10 output classes (one for each *CIFAR-10* class). Figure 4.1 shows a representation of the CNN.

The `forward` function defines how input data passes through each layer sequentially. The *convolutional layers* use *ReLU activation function* (see Appendix A for details) followed by *max pooling*, and the final *fully connected layer* outputs the class scores. The code checks whether a GPU is available using `torch.cuda.is_available()`³. This is essential for leveraging faster computation during training and evaluation.

```
[2]: class SimpleCNN(nn.Module):
    def __init__(self):
        super(SimpleCNN, self).__init__()
        self.conv1 = nn.Conv2d(3, 16, kernel_size=3, padding=1)
        self.conv2 = nn.Conv2d(16, 32, kernel_size=3, padding=1)
        self.pool = nn.MaxPool2d(2, 2)
        self.fc1 = nn.Linear(32 * 8 * 8, 128)
        self.fc2 = nn.Linear(128, 10)

    def forward(self, x):
        x = self.pool(torch.relu(self.conv1(x)))
        x = self.pool(torch.relu(self.conv2(x)))
        x = x.view(-1, 32 * 8 * 8)
        x = torch.relu(self.fc1(x))
        x = self.fc2(x)
```

³**CUDA** is a proprietary software layer developed by Nvidia for their graphic cards that provides direct access to their virtual instruction set and parallel computational elements.[24]

```

        return x

# Check device
device = torch.device("cuda" if torch.cuda.is_available() else "cpu")
print(f"Using device: {device}")

```

Using device: cuda

We use the `transform` function to convert images into tensors and normalize them, ensuring each color channel has a mean of 0.5 and a standard deviation of 0.5. This step stabilizes and accelerates the training process. The dataset is then downloaded and loaded into training and test sets using *torchvision* and *DataLoader*.

```
[3]: transform = transforms.Compose([
    transforms.ToTensor(),
    transforms.Normalize((0.5, 0.5, 0.5), (0.5, 0.5, 0.5))
])

```

Our dataset is downloaded and loaded for training and test respectively, using *torchvision* and *DataLoader*

```
[4]: train_dataset = datasets.CIFAR10(root='./data', train=True,
    ↪download=True, transform=transform)
test_dataset = datasets.CIFAR10(root='./data', train=False,
    ↪download=True, transform=transform)

train_loader = DataLoader(train_dataset, batch_size=64, shuffle=True)
test_loader = DataLoader(test_dataset, batch_size=64, shuffle=False)

```

Downloading <https://www.cs.toronto.edu/~kriz/cifar-10-python.tar.gz> to
./data\cifar-10-python.tar.gz

Extracting ./data\cifar-10-python.tar.gz to ./data
Files already downloaded and verified

A small function is defined to visualize a selection of images (the first five, in this case) from the dataset along with their labels. To achieve this, the function applies a slight un-normalization, restoring the images to their original appearance for better interpretability.

```
[5]: def show_images(dataset, n=5):
    plt.figure(figsize=(10, 2))
    for i in range(n):
        image, label = dataset[i]
        image = (image / 2 + 0.5).numpy() # Unnormalize
        plt.subplot(1, n, i + 1)
        plt.imshow(image.transpose(1, 2, 0))
        plt.title(f"Label: {label}")
        plt.axis('off')
    plt.show()

show_images(train_dataset)
```


Next, we create an instance of the `SimpleCNN` model and move it to the GPU for faster computations. The *loss function* used is `CrossEntropyLoss` (A.1.2), which is well-suited for multi-class classification problems. The *summary* function provides an overview of the neural network architecture, including the number of parameters and the dimensions of each tensor.

```
[6]: model = SimpleCNN().to(device) # Move model to device
    criterion = nn.CrossEntropyLoss()
    optimizer = optim.Adam(model.parameters(), lr=0.001)

    # Display model structure
    print("Model Summary:")
    summary(model, (3, 32, 32), device=str(device))
```

Model Summary:

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
Conv2d-1	[-1, 16, 32, 32]	448
MaxPool2d-2	[-1, 16, 16, 16]	0

Conv2d-3	[-1, 32, 16, 16]	4,640
MaxPool2d-4	[-1, 32, 8, 8]	0
Linear-5	[-1, 128]	262,272
Linear-6	[-1, 10]	1,290

=====
 Total params: 268,650

Trainable params: 268,650

Non-trainable params: 0

 Input size (MB): 0.01

Forward/backward pass size (MB): 0.24

Params size (MB): 1.02

Estimated Total Size (MB): 1.27

The training loop runs for a fixed number of 5 **epochs**, where an *epoch* represents a complete pass through the training dataset. During training, the model processes data in *batches*. For each *batch*, the images are loaded onto the GPU, and the gradients are reset using the `optimizer.zero_grad()` function. Predictions are then generated for the *batch*, the loss is calculated, and the *backpropagation algorithm* updates the model parameters based on the computed gradients. Once an *epoch* is completed, the average loss is calculated and stored for later plotting.

```
[7]: # Training loop
num_epochs = 5
train_losses = []

for epoch in range(num_epochs):
    running_loss = 0.0
    for images, labels in train_loader:
        images, labels = images.to(device), labels.to(device) #
        ↪ Move data to device
        optimizer.zero_grad()
        outputs = model(images)
        loss = criterion(outputs, labels)
        loss.backward()
        optimizer.step()
        running_loss += loss.item()
```

```
epoch_loss = running_loss / len(train_loader)
train_losses.append(epoch_loss)
print(f"Epoch {epoch + 1}/{num_epochs}, Loss: {epoch_loss:.4f}")

# Plot the loss function
plt.plot(train_losses, label="Training Loss")
plt.xlabel("Epoch")
plt.ylabel("Loss")
plt.title("Training Loss Over Epochs")
plt.legend()
plt.show()
```

```
Epoch 1/5, Loss: 1.4167
Epoch 2/5, Loss: 1.0795
Epoch 3/5, Loss: 0.9349
Epoch 4/5, Loss: 0.8380
Epoch 5/5, Loss: 0.7608
```


After training, the model is evaluated on the test dataset using `model.eval()`. Gradients are disabled during evaluation with `torch.no_grad()`, which reduces memory usage and speeds up computations. The test data is processed batch by batch, and predictions are generated. The predicted class for each image is determined using `torch.max()`, and the overall accuracy is calculated as the percentage of correctly classified images. In this toy example, an accuracy of 68.39% was achieved, which is satisfactory given the simplicity of the model and the purpose of the demonstration.

```
[8]: # Evaluate model accuracy
correct = 0
total = 0
```

```

model.eval()
with torch.no_grad():
    for images, labels in test_loader:
        images, labels = images.to(device), labels.to(device) #
        ↪ Move data to device
        outputs = model(images)
        _, predicted = torch.max(outputs, 1)
        total += labels.size(0)
        correct += (predicted == labels).sum().item()
accuracy = 100 * correct / total
print(f"Final Accuracy on Test Set: {accuracy:.2f}%")

```

Final Accuracy on Test Set: 68.39%

Figure 4.1: A schematic representation of the SimpleCNN architecture used for the example. The input to the model is a $3 \times 32 \times 32$ RGB image. The first *convolutional layer* applies 16 filters of size 3×3 with padding of 1, followed by a *ReLU activation function* and a 2×2 *max-pooling layer* that halves the spatial dimensions. The second *convolutional layer* applies 32 filters of size 3×3 with padding of 1, followed by another *ReLU activation* and a 2×2 *max-pooling layer*, reducing the spatial dimensions further. The output from the second *pooling layer* is flattened into a vector of size 2048, which is passed through a *fully connected layer* that reduces it to 128 dimensions, followed by another *fully connected layer* that maps to 10 output classes.

CNN for the search of LSB galaxies

In this chapter, we introduce the CNN developed for the identification of LSB galaxies, along with simulations and results.

5.1 Libraries

This work used a number of non-standard Python packages throughout the development process. Besides *PyTorch*, which is central to the project, a number of science-oriented tools have been used. The most significant are *Astropy* and *SciPy*. The **Astropy** package contains functionality particularly useful to astronomers and astrophysicists, but is generally useful to anyone writing astronomy-related software. **SciPy** is a library for scientific computing that contains modules for optimization, interpolation, signal processing and more. Another package used here is **GalSim** that allows us to simulate images of space objects (e.g., stars, galaxies) and apply various filters or transformations on them, such as dilation and rotation of a galaxy. In this paper, we used *GalSim* to create the different original datasets used in the experiments.

5.2 Prototypes Using Standard Datasets

Before designing the system to analyze galaxies for LSB galaxies, several prototypes were tested on already available datasets. These prototypes included grayscale and RGB images to establish a robust architecture in the project. The *CIFAR-10* and *MNIST* datasets were employed first. These experiments used deeper versions of the CNN introduced in the previous chapter, achieving higher overall accuracy by making use of additional convolutional layers and more advanced techniques. Later, we used astronomical catalogs specifically designed for neural network training, namely those related to galaxies. Manual classification of real astronomical objects is an onerous process, so assembling a validated dataset with which to train the neural networks becomes very time-consuming. It is, therefore, a motivation for performing citizen

science projects. For example, the *Zooniverse Galaxy Zoo* project¹. Part of the data collected was optimised and released as the *Galaxy10* dataset[25] for training neural networks. There are two versions of *Galaxy10*: an older version using SDSS images and a higher-resolution version using DECaLS² photos. Both contain 10 mutually exclusive classes and were used in this study. This prototypes reached a final accuracy of about 70% on the whole dataset.

Subsequently, an initial batch of simulated data was used to finalize the architecture of the neural network, starting with only bright galaxies and later incorporating LSBs, ultimately resulting in the network described in Section 5.4.

Figure 5.1: Sample images extracted from the *Galaxy10* dataset during a training run. Each class shows distinct morphological features.

5.3 Euclid Simulations

Simulated data were used to train the CNN, given the very high number of images needed. The simulation tool, initially built by Prof. A. Nucita for *Euclid* mission, was utilized to simulate *globular clusters*, galaxies, SSOs³, stars, and background images observed with the VIS instrument. The images are hence 101×101 pixels grayscale. For the purpose of this work, the simulated output objects, and therefore the neural network classes, were *galaxies*, *stars* and *background* (references as Class 1, Class 2 and

¹**Zooniverse** is a citizen science web portal operated by the Citizen Science Alliance. Its first project, Galaxy Zoo was focused on classifying galaxies by morphological features. Since then, *Zooniverse* has launched campaigns across ecology, biology, arts, and climate science.

²The **Dark Energy Camera Legacy Survey (DECaLS)** is an astronomical survey using the *Dark Energy Camera (DECam)*, a large camera on the *Victor M. Blanco* 4m telescope, located at the Cerro Tololo Inter-American Observatory.

³**Solar System Objects** (stars, planets, dwarf planets, moons/satellites, comets, and asteroids)

Class 3, respectively).

Considering the presence of *GalSim*, which is only available in Linux and MacOS versions, the code was run on a dedicated computer locally and subsequently brought to *Google Colab*, so that it can be used completely in the Cloud (with automatic uploading of the generated files) and on other operating systems. The program contains two Python scripts: `make_sim.py` and `LSBModule.py`. A detailed explanation of the functions contained in these scripts is available in Appendix B. We shall mention the critical parameters selected for this work in the following.

5.3.1 Galaxy Simulations

Simulations of galaxies are derived on the basis of the **Sérsic profile**, the mathematical representation for the surface brightness profile of a galaxy. The formula for *Sérsic profile* is:

$$\mu(r) = \mu_e \exp \left(-b_n \left[\left(\frac{r}{r_e} \right)^{1/n} - 1 \right] \right) \quad (5.1)$$

where $\mu(r)$ is the *surface brightness* at radius r , μ_e is the *surface brightness* at the *effective radius* r_e ⁴, n is the *Sérsic index*, which varies depending on the type of galaxy ($n \simeq 1$ for disk galaxies with *exponential profiles*, $n \simeq 4$ for elliptical galaxies with *de Vaucouleurs profiles*), and b_n is a numerical constant that is a function of n , ensuring that the *effective radius* contains half the total light.

The `LSBModule` calculates the intensity $\mu(r)$ for each pixel (x, y) of the image by converting pixel coordinates to elliptical coordinates in order to compensate for eccentricity and inclination. The surface brightness is then calculated using the *Sérsic formula* and normalized. The *Sérsic index* and *half-light radius* were randomly created by the code, along with the position angle and ellipticity. More specifically, for this simulation, r_e was drawn uniformly from between 1 and 2 arcseconds. For a specified surface brightness limit of $\mu = 23 \text{ mag/arcsec}^2$, the galaxy magnitude m for the minimum and maximum values of r_e can be calculated.

The average *surface brightness* μ within the *effective radius* r_e is given by the formula:

$$\mu = m + 2.5 \log_{10}(\pi r_e^2), \quad (5.2)$$

where: μ is again the *surface brightness* in mag/arcsec^2 , m is the *integrated magnitude*⁵ of the galaxy, and r_e is the *half-light radius* in *arcsec*. Rearranging Eq. (5.2), we can

⁴The **effective radius**, or **half-light radius**, r_e , is defined as the radius at which half the total light of a galaxy is emitted.

⁵The **integrated magnitude** is defined as the apparent magnitude an extended object would have if all of its light were concentrated into a point source. When referring to the magnitude of a galaxy in this work, it is implied that it refers to the *integrated magnitude* unless otherwise specified.

solve for the *integrated magnitude* m :

$$m = \mu - 2.5 \log_{10}(\pi r_e^2). \quad (5.3)$$

Case 1: $r_e = 1$ arcsec

$$m = 23 - 2.5 \log_{10}(\pi \cdot 1^2) \simeq 21.76 \quad (5.4)$$

Case 2: $r_e = 2$ arcsec

$$m = 23 - 2.5 \log_{10}(\pi \cdot 2^2) \simeq 20.25. \quad (5.5)$$

Thus, simulated galaxies with $m > 22$ (fainter magnitudes) will have an average *surface brightness* $\mu > 23$ mag/arcsec² and can be classified as LSB galaxies. To improve the network's performance, magnitude values between 14 and 28 were used, with smaller intervals generated for testing purposes.

Figure 5.2: A simulated LSB galaxy displayed in *SAOImage ds9*, an astronomical imaging and data visualization application, alongside its header. Keys such as **TYPE** (object class), **MAG** (magnitude), and **RE** (effective radius) are displayed.

5.3.2 Other Parameters

The range of star magnitudes was similar to that of galaxies, enabling a comparative analysis of confusion between the two populations. The background, however, was taken from real noise from the *Euclid* VIS camera, with an average sky magnitude of around 25 in each image (25.0 ± 0.3 mag extracting the value directly from images). This suggests a significant barrier in detecting astronomical objects whose magnitudes are above this. Taking this into account, an entire dataset of 20001 object was produced⁶. This dataset was split by code into training and testing subsets at a ratio 60% training/40% testing. The other regular practice in machine learning is *data augmentation* to prevent overfitting and to learn the network rotational, translational and scaling invariance. Therefore a set of random transformations is applied to every dataset during training, e.g., horizontal flips, rotations, affine transformations and brightness, contrast, and saturation adjustments (details see C.2.1). An *early stopping* is also used for the same purpose.

Sample images from the dataset

Figure 5.3: Sample images extracted from the simulated dataset.

⁶The sets are one additional in number to those anticipated (i.e., 20001 in place of 20000) due to Python's adoption of zero-based arrays.

5.4 CNN implementation and architecture

The CNN was implemented in Python 3.8 using PyTorch. The training of the CNN was executed on a GeForce RTX 4070 Super paired with a Ryzen 7 7800X3d CPU (refer to Appendix C for technical details).

Since the simulated images are in grayscale and the dimmer galaxies are hidden in pictures, a high number of filters has been used in the final CNN architecture. Using a trial and error strategy, we found that the adequate number of blocks for going beyond the LSB threshold was 6. So the consists of five *convolutional blocks* followed by two *fully connected layers* as shown in Figure 5.4.

Figure 5.4: A diagram illustrating the architecture of the CNN. The diagram is color-coded as follows: *convolutional layers* in yellow, *ReLU activation layers* in orange, *batch normalization layers* in green, *max-pooling layers* in red, and *fully connected and output layers* in cyan. The thick lines represent the connections between these layers.

The thickness of each block is proportional to the depth of the layer in the network, representing either the number of *feature maps* (in *convolutional layers*) or the number of neurons (in *fully connected layers*). For example, the Conv1 layer has a depth of 35, indicating 35 filters while FC1 has a depth of 5, corresponding to 5 neurons. The notations such as I , $I/2$, $I/4$, etc., in the diagram indicate the input size at each layer. Specifically I represents the initial input size, while $I/2$ means that the feature map’s spatial dimensions (height and width) are reduced by half after passing through the layer, due to max-pooling. The same pattern follows for the other blocks. Based on *PlotNeuralNet*[49]

The network begins with a single-channel image, say a grayscale image, and begins with an initial *convolutional block*. To that effect, the first *convolutional layer* uses 32 filters of size 3×3 with padding to preserve spatial dimensions (Figure 5.5). Following that,

batch normalization is used and then a *ReLU activation function* to introduce non-linearity in the model. The next *convolutional layer* doubles the feature dimensionality to 64 channels, followed by max pooling that reduces the spatial dimensions by half. To handle *overfitting*, *dropout* regularization is used where randomly chosen neurons are dropped with a 50% probability. In the next block, the network uses 128 filters with the same sequence of convolution, *batch normalization*, *ReLU activation*, and *max pooling* followed by *dropout* for regularization purposes. The third and fourth block once more increases the complexity of the features by doubling the number of filters to 512. The fifth block takes the deepest level of feature extraction, with 1024 filters to detect high-level patterns in the input data. The output of this block is flattened into a one-dimensional vector, preparing it for the *fully connected layers*. The first *fully connected layer* lowers the dimensionality to 256, with *ReLU activation* and introducing a *dropout* rate of 60% for regularization. The second *fully connected layer* lowers the dimensionality further to 128, with *ReLU* and *dropout*. The architecture concludes with an *output layer* that projects the 128-dimensional vector onto four output classes, three of which are object-related and one reserved for debugging.

Figure 5.5: Sample of 32 feature maps extracted by the first convolutional layer during the training of the CNN.

5.5 General results

The training and testing implementation is explained in details in [C.4](#) and [C.5](#) respectively while in this Chapter we will discuss only the results. After training, an accuracy of 87.08% was reached for *integrated magnitude* values from 14 to 28. To show the

way the CNN label the data, we can use the ROC curves introduced in Chapter 2 for every class. These are shown in Figure 5.6 and are computed during training with the function outlined in C. As is apparent, the *Area Under the Curve* (AUC) scores are all very good, with Class 1 achieving 0.98, indicating excellent separability. Classes 2 and 3 have slightly poorer AUC scores of 0.94, indicating strong but less accurate performance. These results can be interpreted using another type of visual graph called the **confusion matrix**, also referred to as the *Error matrix*. As the name suggests, this is what is depicted in this matrix, i.e., that each row of the matrix corresponds to instances of a true class, and each column corresponds to instances of a predicted class (or vice versa). Thus the diagonal terms of the matrix depict all examples that are perfectly predicted by the CNN. The matrix is shown in Figure 5.7: the CNN shows strong performance with high values for all three classes: 2388 for Class 1, 1984 for Class 2, and 2641 for Class 3. However, the matrix also highlights some misclassifications, with notable confusion between Class 2 and Class 3, where 608 instances of Class 2 were misclassified as Class 3. These errors can be easily interpreted as very low magnitude galaxies which are too faint for the CNN to be recognize and so are confuse with the background of the images, and, in some cases, completely obscured by the background itself. These limitation will be discussed in the next sections.

Figure 5.6: ROC curves for the main dataset.

Figure 5.7: Confusion matrix for the main dataset.

5.5.1 Performance by magnitude interval

As expected, the performance of our model gradually deteriorates as luminosity decreases. Fainter galaxies become less visible as their magnitude increases. For higher magnitudes, the off-diagonal values in the confusion matrix increase, and the background eventually becomes strongly dominant over the rest. This is particularly true for galaxies, where, beyond a certain threshold, the network’s performance declines, and galaxies are no longer correctly recognized as their $mag/arcsec^2$ is overshadowed by the background.

We can highlight this behavior by analyzing the confusion matrices across various magnitude intervals. Specifically, we divided our range of 14 magnitudes into 7 sub-intervals of 2 magnitudes each. We then tested the already trained and validated network on these additional datasets, consisting of 2001 simulated objects. Note that in these datasets, the magnitude range of the stars remains unchanged, as does the background, which is based on *Euclid* true noise. This setup allows us to compare the model’s performance for galaxies relative to other classes.

Magnitude 14-16

The CNN performs very well, with only 85 off-diagonal objects (Figure 5.8). Interestingly, the vast majority of these are stars predicted as background. An inspection

revealed that these are very bright stars with small apparent radii, appearing as point-like objects in the images. The simplest explanation is that they are easily confused with the background and considered random fluctuations because they are bright but visually compact objects. Their low number in the selected magnitude range during training likely prevented the network from recognizing them adequately. However, since these are stars and their classification is outside the scope of this study, this issue does not affect our analysis of galaxies.

Magnitude 16-18

For magnitudes between 16 and 18, the model performs exceptionally well, with near-perfect classification (99.2% correct predictions). There are only 15 false positives for galaxies, as shown in Figure 5.9. This error rate is negligible.

Magnitude 18-20

In this range, the model continues to perform strongly, with only 10 background objects misclassified as galaxies (Figure 5.10).

Magnitude 20-22

In this range, the model maintains strong performance, with only 10 background objects misclassified as galaxies (Figure 5.11). Some galaxies in this range may already be considered LSBs, as discussed in Subsection 5.3.1. However, their effective number should remain relatively small in this range.

Magnitude 22-24

At these magnitudes, only LSB galaxies are expected. As anticipated, the model's performance begins to decline, as shown in Figure 5.12. The accuracy for Class 2 (galaxies) decreases notably due to the increasing difficulty in distinguishing features at higher magnitudes. Specifically, 41 galaxies are predicted as stars and 61 as background, i.e. for Class 2 84.5% of the predictions are correct. This behavior could potentially be attributed to higher or smaller *effective radii* as the magnitude increases. We will explore this possibility in 5.7.2.

Magnitude 24-26

Figure 5.13 shows a further drop in performance at this faint magnitude range (28.9% correct previsions, compatible with guessing). Class 2 experiences significant accuracy degradation, with many misclassifications into both Class 1 (stars) and Class 3 (background). False negatives between galaxies and the background outnumber correct predictions. This is expected, as these LSB galaxies become indistinguishable from the

background even for human observers. The background has a value of approximately $25 \text{ mag}/\text{pixel}$. Taking in account randomness, this value is generally comparable to or even higher than the surface brightness of simulated galaxies, which are thus obscured by the noise.

Magnitude 26-28

As predicted, at this magnitude range, 94% of galaxies are misclassified by the CNN (Figure 5.14). For such extremely low luminosity values, it becomes impossible to distinguish these objects from the background, and smaller galaxies are often identified as stars. In this magnitude range, a CNN of this type reaches its limitations.

Observations

In summary, the performance of the CNN shows a clear dependence on galaxy magnitude. While the model achieves high accuracy for brighter galaxies, its ability to correctly classify objects declines as magnitude increases, particularly beyond 25 mag. This behavior is consistent with the increasing dominance of background noise at fainter magnitudes, which obscures the features necessary for classification.

Figure 5.8: Confusion Matrix for magnitude interval 14-16

Figure 5.9: Confusion Matrix for magnitude interval 16-18

Figure 5.10: Confusion Matrix for magnitude interval 18-20

Figure 5.11: Confusion Matrix for magnitude interval 20-22

Figure 5.12: Confusion Matrix for magnitude interval 22-24

Figure 5.13: Confusion Matrix for magnitude interval 24-26

Figure 5.14: Confusion Matrix for magnitude interval 26-28

5.6 Higher luminosities performance

The magnitude range between 14 and 22 represents the regime where the CNN focuses on analyzing higher-luminosity objects. Within this interval, the network is expected to learn features that can later be applied to higher-magnitude galaxies. This section provides a detailed analysis of the results in this range, emphasizing the consistency of the predictions, the nature of the rare misclassifications observed, and the potential factors contributing to the network's strong performance. By understanding the model's behavior in this optimal range, we can better contextualize the limitations observed in the lower luminosity regime.

A dataset containing 5000 galaxy-only samples was simulated and used for testing. The confusion matrix in Figure 5.15 shows that the model correctly classified the vast majority of samples (4996), with only a very small number (5) misclassified as Class 1. Overall, the model demonstrates excellent performance, achieving near-perfect accuracy for Class 2. This performance suggests that the network has successfully learned to recognize the distinct patterns of high-luminosity galaxies within the 14-22 magnitude range. Results suggest that the model could generalize well to similar luminosity regimes, but further testing on real data or higher-magnitude ranges is needed.

Figure 5.15: Confusion matrix for higher luminosity galaxies. Only 5 galaxies has been incorrectly predicted as stars.

5.7 LSB performance

Analyzing the CNN performance in the magnitude range 22-28, with the same modality as discussed in the previous section, the confusion matrix reveals a significant increase in misclassifications compared to the performance observed in the lower magnitude ranges. While the CNN performs well up to a magnitude of 24, as seen in 5.5.1, the fainter galaxies in this interval present greater challenges. Specifically, the model correctly classifies 2003 samples of Class 2 but misclassifies 202 samples as Class 1 and 2796 samples as Class 3. This marks a considerable decline in accuracy compared to the near-perfect results in the 14-22 magnitude range.

The increase in misclassifications can be attributed to the reduced *signal-to-noise ratio* at higher magnitudes, which complicates the extraction of discriminative features. The large number of Class 2 samples incorrectly predicted as Class 3 is compatible with the fact that the features of faint galaxies become increasingly difficult to distinguish from the background in this range. Furthermore, changing the network weights doesn't change the behavior of the net.

Figure 5.16: Confusion matrix for Class 2 objects which are surely LSB galaxies given their magnitude. The misclassification here is evident.

Despite these limitations, the results underline the robustness of the network up to a magnitude of 24 as suggested in 5.5.1. Beyond this threshold, the increasing noise make extremely difficult for both machine and human to differentiate between galaxy and only background in our dataset leading to the complete disappearance of patterns in images that can be used by the network.

5.7.1 Accuracy limit

To establish how the network behave until an *accuracy limit* make difficult to distinguish between Class 2 and Class 3, it's possible to use a fixed *integrated magnitude* dataset. The previous result suggested that at magnitude 24 the CNN become less accurate in predicting the presence of LSB galaxies. With this fixed value, the model correctly classifies 2993 samples as Class 2, while 240 samples are misclassified as Class 1, and 1768 samples are misclassified as Class 3. At this magnitude $\sim 3/5$ of the galaxies are still correctly identified.

Going further, with a fixed *integrated magnitude* of 24.5 it is possible to see that the situation is the opposite, with 1998 galaxies correctly recognized ($\sim 2/5$) and 2993 incorrectly. In particular 2773 are identified as background. The accuracy limit at which the CNN recognizes an equal number of galaxies as correct and incorrect, i.e. the limit for which the model splits the galaxies in half correctly identified and half misclassified, should be around magnitude 24.25. This is easily corroborated by using this as a fixed magnitude: there are 2438 LSB galaxies correctly identified and 2563 wrongly classified.

Given Eq. (5.2), this magnitude value corresponds to a surface brightness of 25.49 $mag/arcsec^2$ and 27.00 $mag/arcsec^2$ for *half-light radius* of 1 $arcsec$ and 2 $arcsec$, respectively (for $r_e = 1.5 arcsec$, $\mu = 26.37 mag/arcsec^2$). This value is clearly higher than the average magnitude found for the background (25 $mag/arcsec^2$).

The performance at this magnitude highlights a critical threshold at which the model begins to encounter significant challenges in distinguishing between classes. The large number of misclassifications as Class 3 suggests that the features extracted from galaxies at this magnitude begin to resemble only-background images. Although magnitude 24.25 marks the transition to more significant errors, the results still demonstrate the ability of the model to extract meaningful features at this magnitude.

Figure 5.17: Confusion matrix for a 5000 fixed 24 magnitude dataset of galaxies.

Figure 5.18: Confusion matrix for a 5000 fixed 24.5 magnitude dataset of galaxies.

Figure 5.19: Confusion matrix for a 5000 fixed 24.25 magnitude dataset of galaxies. At this value, about half of the galaxies are correctly identified and half wrongly classified as stars or background.

5.7.2 Effective Radius

A possible explanation for the fact that certain galaxies are recognized is that only galaxies with a small *half-light radius* are visible at this magnitude (mainly, their core). This could be suggested by a human examination of some galaxies contained in previously used datasets. Nevertheless, this hypothesis does not appear to be supported by the data.

With reference to Figure 5.20, the distribution of *effective radii* for correctly classified galaxies (top panel) shows a relatively uniform spread across the range, with no noticeable concentration or bias towards a particular sub-interval of R_E values. Similarly, the distribution for incorrectly classified galaxies (bottom panel) also appears uniform, suggesting that the *effective radius* is not acting as a discriminating factor in the model's predictions. If the *effective radius* were a determining factor, one would expect a divergence between the distributions of correct and incorrect predictions. The lack of such patterns indicates that r_e alone is unlikely to explain the observed classification errors at magnitude 24.25, probably due to the limited values of radius used, ranging between 1 and 2 arcseconds. This result suggests instead that other factors, such as the faintness of galaxies and relatively high background values, are more likely contributors

to the model’s misclassifications.

Figure 5.20: The distribution of *effective radii* (RE) for LSB galaxies at magnitude 24.25, separated into correctly classified (top) and incorrectly classified (bottom) samples. The analysis reveals no clear dependence of classification performance on the *effective radius*, as the distributions appear uniform across r_E values in both cases. The same behavior was observed for lower and higher magnitude values

5.8 Discussion

The CNN model we introduced in this chapter is a robust architecture that has been tailored with particular focus on the requirements of low surface brightness (LSB) galaxy identification. The performance level shows very close to perfect accuracy and high separability within the 14-24 magnitude range. These consistent AUC values and performances across multiple magnitudes confirm the network’s learning and generalization capability in this optimal range. Moreover, the use of confusion matrices and magnitude-based testing permits a good understanding of the network’s classification performance.

However, once the magnitude is higher than 24, the network performance starts to decline, highlighting some predictable weakness in the very low surface brightness regime. Low brightness galaxies being misclassified as background or stars indicate the intrinsic difficulty with decreasing *signal-to-noise ratios* and dominating background. The fixed magnitude analysis corroborate that the accuracy limit is attained at a magnitude of

approximately 24.25, where the correct classifications of galaxies by the network are almost equaled by the misclassifications. The cutoff highlights the challenging nature of classifying faint galaxies against background features, even with an optimized network. Thus, while the CNN is demonstrated to be very efficient in identifying LSB galaxies in some magnitudes ranges, its efficiency at higher magnitudes indicates where it needs to be improved. Training with real data could be a possible method to enable the network to generalize better for example. Moreover, more spectral channels may enhance the performance.

Nevertheless, one of the most significant advantages of the our proposed CNN architecture is its flexibility. With slight adjustments, we may utilize it in other fields of research in astronomy, for instance, the detection of galaxies with *strong gravitational lensing*[26] or the detection of *stellar streams*. All of these applications share the challenge of identifying faint, intricate characteristics in noisy data, so the architectural flexibility is a significant benefit.

5.9 Future prospect: Transformer Neural Network

The results we presented in this chapter affirm the potential of CNNs to revolutionize astronomical data analysis, open the way for more sophisticated and effective methodologies in the detection of faint celestial objects: recent works[27][28] suggested that the use of a **Transformer network** compared to a CNN for astrophysical object recognition could offer several advantages.

CNNs operate mainly on local filters, as been seen, and they can capture global relationships only by stacking many layers. This require greater depth and thus more complexity to achieve a global understanding. *Transformers* are instead able to capture global relationships between all parts of an image: this is clearly useful in astrophysics, where the distinguishing features of an object can be spread across different zones of an image. This is give advantages when used with very large astronomical surveys (e.g., LSST or *Euclid*). However, there are also some factors to consider, such as *Transformers* need large datasets to perform well, whereas CNNs can be trained with smaller ones. *Transformers* also generally require more computational resources and designing a *Transformer* architecture for images is usually more complex compared to CNNs.

Conclusions

In this thesis we demonstrated the potential of *Convolutional Neural Networks* (CNNs) as powerful tools for the detection and classification of LSB galaxies, addressing the limitations of traditional observational techniques. By combining a theoretical exploration of LSB galaxies, neural networks, and CNNs with a practical implementation using PyTorch, this work provides a comprehensive approach to leveraging deep learning in astrophysics. The designed CNN has shown remarkable performance in identifying faint galaxies with high precision and accuracy. We achieved an 84.5% success rate in identifying LSB galaxies with integrated magnitude values between 22 and 24. Still the performance declines significantly (28.8% correct previsions) for magnitudes in the following range of 24 to 26, precisely where background noise starts to dominate, highlighting the limitations of our model.

The flexibility of the proposed methodology makes it also highly adaptable to other astrophysical challenges, such as the detection of *stellar streams*, *open clusters*, *globular clusters* and *strong gravitational lenses*[26], where the identification of faint or diffuse objects presents similar difficulties. Additionally, while the results on simulated datasets are really promising, a crucial next step for this research is to test the network on real-world observational data, evaluating its robustness and performance in handling the complexities of real astronomical surveys.

Beyond the use of CNNs, this work also opens the door to exploring alternative machine learning architectures, such as *Transformer Neural Networks*, which have recently shown great promise in computer vision tasks. These models, could potentially offer a complementary or even superior approach to solving problems in the detection of faint astrophysical structures.

Ultimately, this thesis highlights the major role of deep learning in astrophysical problems and image classification, providing a solid foundation for future studies to further refine and expand the application of advanced neural network architectures in exploring the universe's most elusive and faint structures.

Part III

Appendices

Loss Function, Optimization algorithms & Activation functions

A

In this appendix, the key concept of *loss functions*, *optimizations algorithms* and *activation functions* are discussed for explanatory reason. For a more detailed discussion, please refer to [29],[30], [31] and [32]

A.1 Loss Function

As said in Section 2.3, a **loss function** is a function that compares the predicted output value and the actual target one, measuring the difference between these values. During training, it's used to optimize the parameters by minimize this difference. A small lose imply a better prediction in the model.

Two main types of *loss functions* can be find: **regressions loss functions**, used for continuous outputs, and **classification loss functions**, which are used, as the name suggests for categorical outputs, like image classification. In this section, we'll briefly discuss an example of each type.

A.1.1 Mean Squared Error (MSE)

It's the most simple type of *loss function*. It represents the the *average squared error* and it's defined as

$$\text{MSE} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \tilde{y}_i)^2 \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where y_i is the true value for the i^{th} point while \tilde{y}_i is the predicted one. N is the total number of data points.

Squaring the errors gives higher weight to large deviations. This makes MSE useful in applications where penalizing large errors more heavily is important (e.g., financial predictions, weather forecasting). But the squaring operation also makes MSE easily dominated by extreme values. Also, since MSE depends on the scale of the output variable, the results are not directly comparable across datasets with different ranges.

From (A.1) it's possible to compute the gradient, defined as the derivative of the function.

$$\frac{\partial \text{MSE}}{\partial \tilde{y}_i} = -\frac{2}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \tilde{y}_i) \quad (\text{A.2})$$

A.1.2 Cross-Entropy Loss

Cross-Entropy Loss is another *loss function*. It derives from the concept of *entropy* in information theory.

Entropy is a measure of uncertainty or randomness in a probability distribution. For a true probability distribution $P(y)$, it is defined as:

$$H(P) = - \sum_i P(y_i) \log(P(y_i)) \quad (\text{A.3})$$

Entropy is minimized when the distribution is certain and maximized when the distribution is uniform (all outcomes equally likely). *Cross-entropy* extends entropy to measure the divergence between two distributions: the *true distribution* P and the *predicted distribution* Q .

$$H(P, Q) = - \sum_i P(y_i) \log(Q(y_i)) \quad (\text{A.4})$$

This measures the amount of additional uncertainty when using Q to approximate P . In a binary classification, We define *Cross-Entropy Loss* as the function:

$$\text{Cross-Entropy Loss} = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^n [y_i \log(\tilde{y}_i) + (1 - y_i) \log(1 - \tilde{y}_i)] \quad (\text{A.5})$$

For multi-class classification, it generalizes to:

$$\text{Cross-Entropy Loss} = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{k=1}^K y_{i,k} \log(\tilde{y}_{i,k}) \quad (\text{A.6})$$

where y is the true label, \tilde{y} is the predicted probability distribution, N is the number of sample and K the number of classes.

Cross-Entropy Loss penalizes predictions that deviate from the actual probabilities, forcing the model to predict probabilities closer to the ground truth. The logarithmic penalty imply small errors in predictions with high confidence are penalized more heavily, encouraging the model to avoid overconfidence. In small dataset, though the model may *overfit* due to the strong focus on correctly predicting probabilities for each class. If one class also dominates, *Cross-Entropy Loss* may lead the model to favor that class. This can be mitigated with techniques like *class weighting* (an implementation

is shown in C.4).

The gradient function is defined in the multiclass case as

$$\frac{\partial \text{Cross-Entropy}}{\partial \tilde{y}_{i,k}} = -\frac{y_{i,k}}{\tilde{y}_{i,k}} \quad (\text{A.7})$$

That can be also be written as:

$$\frac{\partial \text{Cross-Entropy}}{\partial \tilde{y}_{i,k}} = \begin{cases} -\frac{1}{\tilde{y}_{i,k}} & \text{if class } k \text{ is the true label} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (\text{A.8})$$

So predictions for incorrect classes do not directly affect the gradient (since $y_{i,k} = 0$ for those classes).

A.2 Optimization algorithms

There exist general methods that improve neural network training. One such is the use of *optimization algorithms* to minimize the loss function.

A lot of different optimization algorithms exists and a lot are currently be developed.

A.2.1 Gradient Descent

Gradient Descent is the foundational *optimization algorithm* for training machine learning models. It iteratively adjust parameters in the direction of the negative gradient of the loss function to minimize it. This can be expressed by the rule:

$$\theta := \theta - \eta \nabla_{\theta} L(\theta) \quad (\text{A.9})$$

where θ are the parameters of the model, η is the learning rate and $\nabla_{\theta} L(\theta)$ is the gradient of the loss function with respect to θ . The *Steepest Descent* presented in Chapter 2 can be considered a special case of this algorithm where η is selected to achieve the maximum gain in the direction of the negative gradient.

A.2.2 Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD)

Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) is a variant of traditional gradient descent. Instead of calculating the gradient using the entire dataset, *SGD* updates model parameters using a single data point at a time. This makes it computationally more efficient and faster for large datasets. The rule become

$$\theta := \theta - \eta \nabla_{\theta} L(\theta, x_i, y_i) \quad (\text{A.10})$$

where $\nabla_{\theta}L(\theta, x_i, y_i)$ is the gradient of the *loss function* with respect to θ computed for the single point (x_i, y_i) . The learning rate η remains fixed as in the traditional *gradient descent*, so a tuning of the *learning rate* is required, although few solutions exist.

A.2.3 Momentum

Momentum is an improved version of *SGD* where is add an accelerating convergence in the direction of consistent gradients. The updating rule is:

$$v_t = \beta v_{t-1} + \nabla_{\theta}L(\theta) \tag{A.11}$$

$$\theta := \theta - \eta v_t \tag{A.12}$$

where β is the *momentum coefficient* and v_t is the *velocity term*.

A.2.4 AdaGrad (Adaptive Gradient Algorithm)

Another well-known optimization algorithm is **AdaGrad**. *AdaGrad* adapts the *learning rate* for each parameter by scaling it inversely proportional to the square root of the sum of all past squared gradients. This ensures that frequently updated parameters receive smaller updates, while infrequently updated parameters get larger updates. In mathematical terms (using the same notation as before) the iterative rule is:

$$\theta := \theta - \frac{\eta}{\sqrt{G_t + \epsilon}} \nabla_{\theta}L(\theta) \tag{A.13}$$

where η is now the initial *learning rate*, G_t is a diagonal matrix where each diagonal element is the sum of the squares of past gradients for parameter θ_i and ϵ is a small constant to avoid division by zero.

So *AdaGrad* adjusts automatically the *learning rate* differently for each parameter without tuning. All previous iterations gradients are used to influence the current *learning rate*. A major disadvantage of *AdaGrad* is that the rate tend to diminish during time, usually preventing further learning improvements.

A.2.5 Adaptive Moment Estimation (Adam)

Introduced in 2014[33], **Adam** combines the benefits of *Momentum* and *AdaGrad*. It computes adaptive learning rates for each parameter using moving averages of both the gradients and their squared values. *Adam* is currently widely used in machine learning due to its robustness and efficiency.

In *Adam*, two moment are present:

$$m_t = \beta_1 m_{t-1} + (1 - \beta_1) \nabla_{\theta} L(\theta) v_t = \beta_2 v_{t-1} + (1 - \beta_2) \nabla_{\theta} L(\theta)^2 \quad (\text{A.14})$$

where m_t is the moving average gradient (referred as *momentum term* or *first moment*) and v_t is the moving average of squared gradients (*adaptive term* or *second moment*). β_1 and β_2 are two hyperparameters which represent the exponential decay for m_t and v_t respectively.

During initialization of the terms, these tend to zero, so a bias correction is present:

$$\tilde{m}_t = \frac{m_t}{1 - \beta_1^t} \quad \tilde{v}_t = \frac{v_t}{1 - \beta_2^t} \quad (\text{A.15})$$

The parameter update rule in Adam is

$$\theta := \theta - \eta \frac{\tilde{m}_t}{\sqrt{\tilde{v}_t} + \epsilon} \quad (\text{A.16})$$

where ϵ still indicates a small constant added to avoid division by zero.

Adam is a flexible algorithm and has automatic scaling for *learning rate*. *Adam* is generally the default optimizer for the majority of deep learning tasks. Different and more modern iterations of *Adam* exist and a other are currently being developed[34].

A.2.6 A simple comparison between algorithms in a CNN

In *PyTorch*, all previously discussed optimization algorithms are implemented and ready available to use using the `torch.Optim` module (all optimizer are listed on the *PyTorch* website [22]). As an example, we will use a modified version of the code reported in Section 4.4. For the comparison we will use *SGD*, *AdaGrad* and *Adam*. Changing just the sixth input of the code, we can compare the three optimizer.

```
[6]: # Training and evaluation function
def train_and_evaluate(optimizer_name):
    model = SimpleCNN().to(device) # Initialize the model
    criterion = nn.CrossEntropyLoss()

    if optimizer_name == "SGD":
        optimizer = optim.SGD(model.parameters(), lr=0.01,
        ↪momentum=0.9)
    elif optimizer_name == "Adagrad":
        optimizer = optim.Adagrad(model.parameters(), lr=0.01)
    elif optimizer_name == "Adam":
```

```

optimizer = optim.Adam(model.parameters(), lr=0.001)
else:
    raise ValueError("Unsupported optimizer")

print(f"Training with {optimizer_name} optimizer")

# Training loop
num_epochs = 5
train_losses = []

for epoch in range(num_epochs):
    running_loss = 0.0
    for images, labels in train_loader:
        images, labels = images.to(device), labels.to(device) #
↪Move data to device
        optimizer.zero_grad()
        outputs = model(images)
        loss = criterion(outputs, labels)
        loss.backward()
        optimizer.step()
        running_loss += loss.item()

    epoch_loss = running_loss / len(train_loader)
    train_losses.append(epoch_loss)
    print(f"Epoch {epoch + 1}/{num_epochs}, Loss: {epoch_loss:.
↪4f}")

# Evaluate model accuracy
correct = 0
total = 0
model.eval()
with torch.no_grad():
    for images, labels in test_loader:
        images, labels = images.to(device), labels.to(device) #
↪Move data to device
        outputs = model(images)
        _, predicted = torch.max(outputs, 1)
        total += labels.size(0)

```

```

        correct += (predicted == labels).sum().item()

    accuracy = 100 * correct / total
    print(f"Final Accuracy with {optimizer_name}: {accuracy:.2f}%")

    # Plot the loss function
    plt.plot(train_losses, label=f"{optimizer_name} Loss")

# Train and compare optimizers
plt.figure(figsize=(10, 5))
train_and_evaluate("SGD")
train_and_evaluate("Adagrad")
train_and_evaluate("Adam")

plt.xlabel("Epoch")
plt.ylabel("Loss")
plt.title("Training Loss Comparison")
plt.legend()
plt.show()

```

Training with SGD optimizer

```

Epoch 1/5, Loss: 1.5968
Epoch 2/5, Loss: 1.1506
Epoch 3/5, Loss: 0.9635
Epoch 4/5, Loss: 0.8385
Epoch 5/5, Loss: 0.7364
Final Accuracy with SGD: 67.79%

```

Training with Adagrad optimizer

```

Epoch 1/5, Loss: 1.4640
Epoch 2/5, Loss: 1.1584
Epoch 3/5, Loss: 1.0595
Epoch 4/5, Loss: 0.9984
Epoch 5/5, Loss: 0.9537
Final Accuracy with Adagrad: 63.49%

```

Training with Adam optimizer

```

Epoch 1/5, Loss: 1.4521
Epoch 2/5, Loss: 1.1126
Epoch 3/5, Loss: 0.9498
Epoch 4/5, Loss: 0.8460

```

Epoch 5/5, Loss: 0.7679

Final Accuracy with Adam: 68.83%

Adam presents the best accuracy (68.83%) and the most rapid loss curve between the analyze optimizer. As stated, *Adam* is the standard optimizer for the majority of task. This is the reason why we used it in both the CNNs reported in this work (Section 4.4 and Appendix C)

A.3 Activation Functions

In Section 2.2.1 we defined the **activation function** of a node in a neural network as the function that calculates the output of the node based on its individual inputs and their weights, changing the behavior of the network. In the same paragraph, the *sigmoid* function is presented, alongside some of its properties. The *sigmoid* for example allows the model to learn more complex patterns introducing non-linearity and has a smooth gradient. Nevertheless this function in modern application has been used less frequently, most commonly in *hidden layers*. Other alternatives has been developed in recent years for different specific tasks. For an overview, please refer to [35]. In this work, other than sigmoid in Chapter 2, the only activation functions we used is the *ReLU*, which is present in both Section 4.4 and in 5.

A.3.1 Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU)

ReLU (Rectified Linear Unit) is defined as:

$$\text{ReLU}(x) = \frac{x + |x|}{2} = \begin{cases} x & \text{if } x > 0, \\ 0 & \text{if } x \leq 0. \end{cases} \quad (\text{A.17})$$

It's use as a general-purpose *activation function* in modern network. It's very common because it's computationally simple, which mean it's faster in processing. It's not linear as the sigmoid but has a positive gradient for positive input, meaning that the gradients cannot become small as input saturate in extreme ranges, slowing the learning. In CNNs, in particular, it's import to highlight the presence of important features: *ReLU* pass positive values while zeroing so does not introduce additional noise and let the network to focus on the key aspect of the input.

Figure A.1: Python plots of the *ReLU* function (left) and its derivative (right).

Simulation program

In this appendix we will briefly explain the main functions of the simulation program. This code was originally developed by Prof. A. Nucita for the *Euclid Collaboration*. Given the length of the code and the high technical details needed, the program is not shown in the document, but part of it can be consulted on [Google Colab](#), where it has been uploaded to run in a cloud environment and on non-UNIX-based operating systems.

The software is made of two different Python files: `LSBModule.py`, which include functions for generate galaxies, and `make_sim.py`, which contains the main part of the code and includes the FITS generation and parameter setting components.

B.1 `make_sim.py`

First of all, the code load the necessities libraries (including *Astropy*, *Scipy*, and *GalSim*) and the `LSBModule`.

After that, defined a list of functions (some of them are not used in this project):

- `rot90`, `rot180`, `rot270` and `rot`, which, as the name suggest, rotates *NumPy* arrays.
- `raster_line(x0, x1, y0, y1)`, that draws a line between two points in an image using *Bresenham's line algorithm*.
- `makeocr` and `makeSS02D`, two unused functions that simulate a *cosmic ray* or a *SSO (Solar System Object)* streaking in an image respectively.
- `makeKing2D`, a simple funtion to model a *King globular cluster*, also not actively used in this work but useful for potential other projects.
- `orderlists`, which reorders a list to match a specified order based on a mapping scheme.
- `makeDS9Regions` creates a *DS9*-compatible region file for visualizing circles at specified coordinates (also unused).
- `tile`, a function that divides it into smaller tiles an images (unused)

- `bias` that adds a constant bias level to an image and, optionally, a more realistic bias pattern with variations in specific columns.
- `read_noise` generate simulated read noise.
- `defineSpecificProgramOptions`, a function where all ancillary files are specified, like the PSF used for the simulation (taken by *Euclid*).
- `makeit`, the part of the code where parameter are decided, generate the images and relative `header` files, discussed next.

B.1.1 `makeit` function

The `make_it` function is the core part of the script. When started, it initializes an instance of the `ManageVis` (class to handle VIS images and another instance of `PSF_VIS` to manage the Point Spread Function (PSF)).

After verifying the input image, the function reads the multi-extension FITS file using the `LoadVisExtension` method of the `ManageVis` class. This method extracts various extensions, including science data, RMS data, and flags, along with associated headers. The extracted data is then reordered to match the VIS focal plane CCD arrangement. Next, the function extracts general metadata from the first science extension, such as exposure time, zero-point magnitude, matrix dimensions, and pixel scale. These parameters are critical for subsequent simulations, as they define the overall configuration of the image and the physical properties of simulated objects.

The PSF (in this case, from *Euclid*) is loaded from an ancillary FITS file. The file is then read into a *GalSim* image object, the PSF is normalized and assigned a pixel scale that matches the VIS camera pixel size.

With the metadata and PSF prepared, the function begins the simulation process. A loop is set up to generate a specified number of synthetic images, each with a specified magnitude interval or value. In each iteration, the function randomly selects one of three simulation scenarios: a star, a galaxy, or a background image. The chosen scenario determines the type of object to simulate and its properties.

For a star, the function computes the flux based on a randomly generated magnitude and the exposure time. The star is modeled as a point source using a `DeltaFunction` and is convolved with the PSF to produce a realistic appearance. The star is then added to the full image, and metadata about the star (e.g., magnitude) is stored.

For a galaxy, the process is similar. The galaxy's size, shape, ellipticity and effective radius are randomly determined. It is modeled using a *Sérsic profile* (Subsection 5.3.1). The galaxy is also convolved with the PSF before being added to the full image.

For a background image, no objects are simulated. Instead, the function generates an image with only read noise and bias.

Each generated image is added to a FITS HDU list, and metadata about the simulated object is stored in the corresponding FITS headers. Once all simulations are complete, the HDU list is written to a FITS file in the specified output directory.

B.2 LSBModule.py

This module define a series of classes utilized in the main code for generate galaxies.

B.2.1 PSF_VIS

This class handle PSF data. It defines a series of methods.

- `GetPsfTest`, a class that reads a test PSF FITS file. This method iterates over the file's HDUs, extracts PSF images, normalizes them by their total area, and stores them in a list.
- `congrid_new` and `congrid`, that implement resampling of 2D arrays (PSFs) to new dimensions using various interpolation methods.
- `ReadPSFCube`, a class that, as the name suggest, reads a PSF cube, handling either single-test PSFs or multi-extension PSF files.

B.2.2 FFPGeometry

It's the class that models the *Full Focal Plane* (FFP), simulating the layout of CCDs. Key methods include:

- `GetRectIntesection` computes the intersection of two rectangles and provides the coordinates of the overlapping region.
- `getFFPGeometry` defines the geometry of the FFP, generating a list of CCD regions with their corners defined in pixel coordinates.
- `DefineStampFrame` creates a rectangular stamp (region of interest) and returns its pixel coordinates.
- `MakeFFPplot` let the user to visualize the FFP layout using *Matplotlib*, marking CCDs and a given stamp for debugging.
- `FromCCD2FFPA` and `FromFFPA2FOV` perform coordinate transformations between CCD, FFP, and *Field of View* (FoV) frames.

B.2.3 GalaxyCreation

This class generate simulated galaxies. Its methods are:

- `gammainc` and `gamma` classes compute the incomplete and complete gamma functions respectively.
- `get_bn`: Solves for the b_n parameter in the *Sérsic profile* (Eq. (5.3)).
- `makeSersic` and `makeSersicProfile` generate the *Sérsic profile*.
- `makeKing2D`, which implements a *King profile* for simulating *globular clusters* (unused)
- `LumDistance` and `FromLinearDistance2AngularDistance` enables *redshift* calculations.

B.2.4 TableFitsHandler

The `TableFitsHandler` manages tabular data in FITS and ASCII formats. The defined method:

- `readAsciiTable` reads an ASCII table and returns an *Astropy* Table object.
- `Table2Fits` instead converts an *Astropy* Table to a FITS file.
- `readFitsTable` is the method that reads a FITS table and extracts column information.
- `getColumn` retrieves a single column from an *Astropy* Table as a *NumPy* array.
- `getColum`, `FindMultipleOccurrences`, `intersection` and `intersection_single` implement set-based operations like finding intersections and duplicate elements in lists.

B.2.5 TableFitsHandler

The class the handle data from the *Euclid* VIS instrument. It presents a long series of methods:

- `LoadVisExtension` is responsible for loading VIS focal plane data and related metadata from FITS files.
- `GetTransformMatrix` retrieves the astrometric transformation matrix for each CCD. The transformation matrix maps pixel coordinates to celestial coordinates (RA/Dec) using FITS data. The transformation includes scaling, rotation, and distortion corrections.

- `Pix2RaDec` and `RaDec2Pix`: the first converts pixel coordinates from the CCD frame into celestial coordinates (RA and Dec) in the *International Celestial Reference System* (ICRS), the second function instead performs the reverse operation.
- `isSourceONCCD`, which checks whether a given source (specified by its RA and Dec) falls within the boundaries of a particular CCD.
- `MakeDummyImage`, that creates a 2D array filled with zeros.
- `getImageStatistics` computes basic statistical metrics for an input image (e.g. mean, median, standard deviation,...)
- `FindCCDID`, a class that determines the CCD ID for a given source based on its RA and Dec.
- `compute_2Dindex` and `compute_1Dindex`. The first maps a CCD index in the range [1–36] to a 2D index (i, j) in the Full Focal Plane (FFP) array. The indices (i, j) correspond to the row and column positions of the CCD in the 6×6 grid of the VIS instrument. `compute_1Dindex` method performs the reverse operation instead.
- `parseCCDID`, which parses a CCD ID string and extracts its row and column indices (i, j). For example, the CCD ID "3-5" corresponds to the CCD in the 3rd row and 5th column of the FFP grid.
- `from1DCCDindex2_HDUindex`, a function that maps a 1D CCD index (1–36) to the corresponding HDU index in the FITS file.
- `isSourceONCCDCheckingGaps` for extending `isSourceONCCD` by checking not only whether a source is on a CCD but also whether it is near the CCD's gaps.
- `FindCCDIDCheckingGaps`, a class that combines the functionality of both `FindCCDID` and `isSourceONCCDCheckingGaps`.
- `locate_stamp` places a rectangular stamp (region of interest) on the VIS focal plane using a specific procedure. It calculates the position of the stamp based on its size and center coordinates.
- `printout` outputs information about the CCDs and stamps in the FFP.

Full CNN Code

In this appendix we will present in detail the code that implements the neural network explained in Chapter 5. As mentioned, the implementation was done using PyTorch as the main library. The IDE chosen was PyCharm. The code is made available under CC BY-SA license [online](#).

C.1 Libraries

The list of libraries required for the correct functioning of the code is the following. Obviously, *PyTorch* and *Astropy* are present, among others, in addition to the standard Python ones.

```
import os
import torch
import torch.nn as nn
from torch.utils.data import Dataset, DataLoader
from torch.optim.lr_scheduler import ReduceLROnPlateau,
    CosineAnnealingLR, OneCycleLR
import torchvision.transforms as transforms
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import numpy as np
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from torchsummary import summary
from astropy.io import FITS
from sklearn.metrics import roc_curve, auc, confusion_matrix,
    ConfusionMatrixDisplay, RocCurveDisplay
from sklearn.exceptions import UndefinedMetricWarning
from collections import Counter
import warnings
import math
```

C.2 Dataset loading

The `download_and_prepare_dataset` function handle the loading of FITS files. These are structured collections of data tables and images, each contained in an HDU (*Header/-*

Data Units). The code reads the HDUs, extracts the image data, and applies a reshaping and normalization. Each image is indeed reshaped into a 3D array of dimensions (101, 101, 1), where the first two dimensions represent the spatial resolution, and the third dimension explicitly defines a single channel (grayscale). The images are then normalized to a [0, 1] range by dividing the raw pixel values by 255.0. This two preliminary steps ensures numerical stability during training, allowing the model to converge more effectively.

The labels are extracted from the FITS headers under the TYPE keyword, in this case a numerical value which identifies the class of the object. These labels are converted to integers for compatibility with PyTorch's `CrossEntropyLoss`, which expects integer targets.

```
def download_and_prepare_dataset():
    # Opens a FITS file and extracts images and labels.
    images, labels = [], []
    with FITS.open('data_new_20000_14_28.FITS') as HDU1:
        for HDU in HDU1:
            if HDU.data is not None:
                # Reshape the image to include a channel dimension.
                images.append(HDU.data.reshape(101, 101, 1))
                # Extract the label from the header and ensure it's
                # an integer.
                label = HDU.header['TYPE'].strip()
                labels.append(int(label))
    # Normalize image data to [0, 1] range and convert labels to
    # integers.
    return np.array(images).astype('float32') / 255.0, np.array(
        labels, dtype='int64')
```

C.2.1 Data augmentation and data loader

`compute_dataset_statistics` calculates the mean and standard deviation of the dataset, which are used to normalize the data further. This additional normalization centers the data distribution, accelerating training and improving numerical stability even more. These statistics are computed over all spatial dimensions (height and width) and across all images.

```
"""Compute mean and standard deviation for normalization"""
def compute_dataset_statistics(images):
    mean = np.mean(images, axis=(0, 1, 2))
    std = np.std(images, axis=(0, 1, 2))
    return mean, std
```

Data augmentation is implemented through the `create_transforms` function. The transformations applied to the training data include random horizontal flips, random rotations of up to 20 degrees, affine transformations that scale the image between 80% and 120% of its original size, and random adjustments to brightness, contrast, and saturation with a maximum adjustment factor of 30%. These operations artificially increase the diversity of the training set by introducing variations in the input images, helping the model generalize better and reducing the risk of *overfitting*. Also the augmentations are stochastic, ensuring that each *epoch* sees a slightly different version of the dataset. The *RandomErasing* augmentation, in particular, randomly remove parts of the image, with the removed area ranging from 2% to 33% of the image size and aspect ratios ranging from 0.3 to 3.3. This forces the model to focus on the global structure of the data rather than small localize features. For test data, only normalization is applied instead because consistency is needed during evaluation to ensure that performance metrics are not biased by augmentation artifacts.

```

"""Define transformations for the training set for data augmentation.
    """
def create_transforms(mean, std):
    # Define transformations for the training set.
    train_transform = transforms.Compose([
        transforms.ToPILImage(), # Convert numpy array to PIL image.
        transforms.RandomHorizontalFlip(), # Randomly flip images
            horizontally.
        transforms.RandomRotation(20), # Apply random rotations.
        transforms.RandomAffine(degrees=0, scale=(0.8, 1.2)), #
            Random affine transformations.
        transforms.ColorJitter(brightness=0.3, contrast=0.3,
            saturation=0.3), # Adjust color properties.
        transforms.ToTensor(), # Convert PIL image to tensor.
        transforms.Normalize(mean=mean.tolist(), std=std.tolist()),
            # Normalize using dataset statistics.
        transforms.RandomErasing(scale=(0.02, 0.33), ratio=(0.3, 3.3)
            ) # Cutout
    ])
    # Define transformations for the test set (only normalization).
    test_transform = transforms.Compose([
        transforms.ToPILImage(),
        transforms.ToTensor(),
        transforms.Normalize(mean=mean.tolist(), std=std.tolist()),
    ])
    return train_transform, test_transform

```

The custom PyTorch CustomDataset class provide an interface to apply transforma-

tions. It overrides the `__len__` method to return the dataset size and the `__getitem__` method to retrieve individual samples by index. The dataset remains compatible with PyTorch's *DataLoader*.

```

"""Custom PyTorch Dataset for loading images and their labels."""
class CustomDataset(Dataset):
    def __init__(self, images, labels, transform=None):
        # Store images, labels, and optional transforms.
        self.images = images
        self.labels = labels
        self.transform = transform

    def __len__(self):
        # Return the total number of samples in the dataset.
        return len(self.images)

    def __getitem__(self, idx):
        # Retrieve an image and its label by index.
        image = self.images[idx]
        label = self.labels[idx]
        # Apply transformation, if defined.
        if self.transform:
            image = self.transform(image)
        return image, label

```

The `create_data_loaders` function splits the dataset into training and testing subsets, with a ratio 60% training and 40% testing.

```

"""Create data loaders for training and testing sets"""
def create_data_loaders(images, labels, train_transform,
    test_transform):
    images_train, images_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(
        images, labels, train_size=0.6)
    train_ds = CustomDataset(images_train, y_train, transform=
        train_transform)
    test_ds = CustomDataset(images_test, y_test, transform=
        test_transform)

    train_loader = DataLoader(train_ds, batch_size=64, shuffle=True,
        num_workers=0)
    test_loader = DataLoader(test_ds, batch_size=64, shuffle=False,
        num_workers=0)
    return train_loader, test_loader

```

C.3 CNN definition

The `build_cnn_model` function defines the deep convolutional neural network described in Section 5.4. This model consists of several *convolutional blocks*, each designed to extract increasingly complex features from the input images. The first block applies a *convolutional layer* with 32 filters of size 3×3 , followed by batch normalization and a *ReLU activation function*. These operations are repeated in subsequent blocks, with the number of filters increasing progressively to 64, 128, 256, 512, and eventually 1024. This gradual increase in the number of filters allows the model to capture both low-level features and high-level features. Each block ends with a *max-pooling layer*, which reduces the spatial dimensions by a factor of 2×2 , effectively halving the height and width of the *feature maps*. This down-sampling helps reduce computational complexity while retaining the most important features. *Dropout layers*, with *dropout* probabilities ranging from 0.5 to 0.6, are interspersed throughout the network to prevent *overfitting* by randomly deactivating neurons during training.

The final layers of the CNN include a global *average pooling* layer that reduces the spatial dimensions of the *feature maps* to a single value for each channel, followed by three *fully connected layers*. The first two *fully connected layers* have 256 and 128 neurons, respectively, and use *ReLU activations* along with 60% dropout. The final layer outputs a vector of size 4, corresponding to the number of classes in the dataset.

```
def build_cnn_model():
    # Define a convolutional neural network with 3 convolutional
    # blocks and 2 fully connected layers.
    return nn.Sequential(
        nn.Conv2d(1, 32, kernel_size=3, padding=1), # Convolutional
            layer with 32 filters
        nn.BatchNorm2d(32), # Batch normalization
        nn.ReLU(), # Activation function
        nn.Conv2d(32, 64, kernel_size=3, padding=1),
        nn.BatchNorm2d(64),
        nn.ReLU(),
        nn.MaxPool2d(2, 2), # Max pooling reduces spatial dimensions
        nn.Dropout(0.5), # Dropout for regularization

        nn.Conv2d(64, 128, kernel_size=3, padding=1),
        nn.BatchNorm2d(128),
        nn.ReLU(),
        nn.Conv2d(128, 128, kernel_size=3, padding=1),
        nn.BatchNorm2d(128),
        nn.ReLU(),
        nn.MaxPool2d(2, 2),
        nn.Dropout(0.5),
```

```

nn.Conv2d(128, 256, kernel_size=3, padding=1),
nn.BatchNorm2d(256),
nn.ReLU(),
nn.Conv2d(256, 256, kernel_size=3, padding=1),
nn.BatchNorm2d(256),
nn.ReLU(),
nn.MaxPool2d(2, 2),
nn.Dropout(0.5),

nn.Conv2d(256, 512, kernel_size=3, padding=1),
nn.BatchNorm2d(512),
nn.ReLU(),
nn.Conv2d(512, 512, kernel_size=3, padding=1),
nn.BatchNorm2d(512),
nn.ReLU(),
nn.MaxPool2d(2, 2),
nn.Dropout(0.5),

nn.Conv2d(512, 1024, kernel_size=3, padding=1),
nn.BatchNorm2d(1024),
nn.ReLU(),
nn.Conv2d(1024, 1024, kernel_size=3, padding=1),
nn.BatchNorm2d(1024),
nn.ReLU(),
nn.AdaptiveAvgPool2d((1, 1)), # Global average pooling
nn.Flatten(), # Flatten the feature maps into a single
               vector

nn.Linear(1024, 256),
nn.ReLU(),
nn.Dropout(0.6),
nn.Linear(256, 128),
nn.ReLU(),
nn.Dropout(0.6),
nn.Linear(128, 4)
)

```

C.4 Training

Training the model involves the function `train`. The *optimizer* used is *Adam*, initialized with a learning rate of 0.003. A `OneCycleLR` learning rate *scheduler* dynamically adjusts the learning rate during training, starting low, increasing to a peak, and then decreasing again. This cycle improves the training stability and performance.

The training loop also implements a *gradient clipping*, limiting the gradient norm to a maximum of 1.0, which prevents gradient explosion during backpropagation. The loss function used is `CrossEntropyLoss`, weighted by class frequencies to handle the imbalance in the dataset. The weights are computed as inversely proportional to the frequency of each class, with optional adjustments to emphasize or de-emphasize specific classes (e.g., doubling the weight for class 2 and multiplying the weight for class 3 by 1.5), available using `compute_class_weight` function.

```
def compute_class_weights(labels, num_classes):
    """Compute weights for each class inversely proportional to class
       frequencies."""
    class_counts = Counter(labels)
    total_samples = len(labels)
    weights = [total_samples / class_counts[i] if i in class_counts
               else 0 for i in range(num_classes)]

    # Adjust weights to emphasize class 3 more than class 2
    weights[2] *= 2 # Increase weight for class 3
    weights[3] *= 1.5 # Decrease weight for class 2
    return torch.tensor(weights, dtype=torch.float32)
```

Several variables are initialized to track the training process. `best_loss` is set to infinity as a placeholder for the best validation loss encountered during training. This variable will be updated whenever a new, lower validation *loss* is observed. `no_improvement` is initialized to zero and acts as a counter for *epochs* without improvement in validation *loss*, which is used to trigger early stopping. Lists `train_losses` and `test accuracies` are used to record the training *loss* and test accuracy for each *epoch*, providing a historical view of the training process. Additional variables such as `best_labels`, `best_preds`, and `best_probs` are initialized to store the predictions and probabilities corresponding to the best-performing model.

The core of the function lies in the *epoch* loop, which iterates for a maximum of `epochs` times (defaulting to 100). At the beginning of each *epoch*, the model is set to training mode with `network.train()`. This ensures that certain layers, such as dropout, are activated, which adds regularization by randomly deactivating neurons during training. The `running_loss` variable is reset to zero at the start of each *epoch* to accumulate the total *loss* over all batches in the current *epoch*.

The function then enters the inner loop, which iterates over the batches of data provided by `train_loader`. Before processing each batch, the *gradients* of the *optimizer* are zeroed out using `optimizer.zero_grad()`. This is necessary to avoid incorrect updates.

The forward pass is executed next, where the batch of images is passed through the

network to generate predictions. The *loss* for the batch is computed by comparing these predictions to the true labels using the weighted `CrossEntropyLoss` function. The `loss.backward()` call performs the backward pass, calculating the gradients of the *loss* with respect to each parameter in the network. These gradients are then clipped using `torch.nn.utils.clip_grad_norm_` to ensure they do not exceed a maximum norm of 1.0. Gradient clipping is an important step in preventing gradient explosion, a common issue in deep learning that can cause unstable updates and lead to divergence. After gradient clipping, the *optimizer* performs a step to update the model's parameters based on the calculated gradients. The batch loss is added to `running_loss`, which accumulates the total training loss for the *epoch*. Once all batches in the *epoch* have been processed, the average training *loss* for the *epoch* is calculated by dividing `running_loss` by the number of batches (`len(train_loader)`). This value is appended to the `train_losses` list for tracking purposes.

With the training phase of the *epoch* complete, the function evaluates the model on the test dataset using the `evaluate_with_metrics` function. This evaluation computes the *validation loss*, accuracy, true labels, predicted labels, and predicted probabilities for the test set. The accuracy for the *epoch* is appended to the `test accuracies` list for historical tracking.

The learning rate *scheduler* is then updated based on the *validation loss*. This dynamic adjustment ensures that the learning rate is tuned to the current state of training, improving the chances of convergence. If the validation loss for the current *epoch* is lower than the best loss observed so far, the function updates `best_loss` to the current *validation loss* and resets the `no_improvement` counter to zero. Additionally, the model's state, along with the corresponding labels, predictions, and probabilities, is saved as the best-performing model state. If the *validation loss* does not improve, the `no_improvement` counter is incremented. If the counter reaches the specified `patience value` (defaulting to 5), the training loop terminates early. This mechanism prevents *overfitting* by halting training once the model stops improving on the validation set, saving both time and computational resources.

At the end of each *epoch*, a summary of the *epoch's* performance is printed, including the *epoch* number, average training loss, validation loss, and accuracy. This provides immediate feedback on how the model is progressing.

When training concludes the model is reset to the best-performing state saved during training. The function then returns the historical training losses, test accuracies, and the labels, predictions, and probabilities associated with the best model.

```
"""Trains the CNN model with early stopping and learning rate
scheduling."""
def train(network, train_loader, test_loader, epochs=100, lr=0.003,
patience=5, device="cuda", class_weight=None):
```

```
optimizer = torch.optim.Adam(network.parameters(), lr=lr)
scheduler = OneCycleLR(optimizer, max_lr=0.005, epochs=epochs,
    steps_per_epoch=len(train_loader))
criterion = nn.CrossEntropyLoss(weight=class_weight.to(device))
    # Weighted loss function

best_loss = float('inf')
no_improvement = 0

train_losses = []
test accuracies = []
best_labels, best_preds, best_probs = None, None, None

for epoch in range(epochs):
    network.train()
    running_loss = 0.0

    for batch, label in train_loader:
        batch, label = batch.to(device), label.to(device)
        optimizer.zero_grad()
        output = network(batch)
        loss = criterion(output, label)
        loss.backward()

        # Gradient clipping to prevent gradient explosion
        torch.nn.utils.clip_grad_norm_(network.parameters(),
            max_norm=1.0)

        optimizer.step()
        running_loss += loss.item()

    avg_train_loss = running_loss / len(train_loader)
    train_losses.append(avg_train_loss)

    # Evaluate and check for improvements
    validation_loss, accuracy, all_labels, all_preds, all_probs =
        evaluate_with_metrics(
            network, test_loader, num_classes=4, device=device
        )
    test accuracies.append(accuracy)

    scheduler.step(float(validation_loss))

    if validation_loss < best_loss:
        best_loss = validation_loss
        no_improvement = 0
```

```

        best_model_state = network.state_dict()
        best_labels, best_preds, best_probs = all_labels,
            all_preds, all_probs
    else:
        no_improvement += 1

    if no_improvement >= patience:
        print("Early stopping...")
        break

    print(
        f"Epoch [{epoch + 1}/{epochs}], Train Loss: {
            avg_train_loss:.4f}, Validation Loss: {validation_loss
                :.4f}, Accuracy: {accuracy:.2f}%"
    )

    network.load_state_dict(best_model_state)
    return train_losses, test accuracies, best_labels, best_preds,
        best_probs

```

C.5 Testing

The `evaluate_with_metrics` function computes key metrics such as average loss, accuracy, and class probabilities. It also collects predictions and labels for further analysis. Visualization functions, like `plot_metrics`, generate confusion matrices and ROC curves for each class, offering insights into the model's performance.

The evaluation process begins by switching the model into evaluation mode using `network.eval()`. The function then initializes several variables: `all_probs` is a list that will store the predicted class probabilities for all batches, while `all_preds` and `all_labels` store the predicted labels and true labels, respectively. `total_loss` is initialized to zero and will accumulate the batch-wise *loss* values, while `correct` and `total` track the number of correct predictions and the total number of samples processed, respectively. The *loss* function used is instantiated as `nn.CrossEntropyLoss()`.

The main loop iterates over batches of data. The network performs a forward pass, generating raw *logits*, which are unnormalized scores representing the model's prediction for each class. The batch *loss* is calculated using `criterion`, where `output` represents the *logits* and `label` contains the true class indices. The batch loss is added to `total_loss`, contributing to the overall validation loss.

The logits are then passed through the `softmax` function, which converts the raw scores into probabilities. These probabilities are stored in `all_probs` as arrays. The predicted labels for each sample in the batch are determined using `torch.max(probs, 1)`, which identifies the class with the highest probability. `predicted` contains the indices of the

predicted classes and is appended to `all_preds`.

To calculate accuracy, the predicted labels are compared with the true labels. The sum of true values represents the number of correct predictions, which is added to the correct counter. Simultaneously, the number of samples in the batch is added to the total counter.

As the loop iterates through all batches, the true labels from each batch are appended to `all_labels`. This aggregation ensures that at the end of the loop, the function has a complete record of true labels, predicted labels, and predicted probabilities for all samples in the dataset. Once all batches have been processed, the total validation loss is calculated by dividing `total_loss` by the number of batches (`len(dataloader)`). This provides the average validation loss, which quantifies the model's overall error in predicting the test set.

The overall accuracy is calculated as $(correct/total) \cdot 100$, giving the percentage of samples correctly classified by the model. Finally, the lists are concatenated into unified arrays using `np.concatenate()`.

```

"""Evaluate the model on test set"""
def evaluate_with_metrics(network, dataloader, num_classes, device="
    cuda"):
    """Evaluate the network and return validation loss, labels,
        predictions, probabilities, and accuracy."""
    network.eval()
    all_probs = []
    all_preds = []
    all_labels = []
    total_loss = 0.0
    correct = 0
    total = 0
    criterion = nn.CrossEntropyLoss()

    with torch.no_grad():
        for batch, label in dataloader:
            batch, label = batch.to(device), label.to(device)
            output = network(batch)
            loss = criterion(output, label)
            total_loss += loss.item()
            probs = torch.softmax(output, dim=1)
            _, predicted = torch.max(probs, 1)

            all_probs.append(probs.cpu().numpy())
            all_preds.append(predicted.cpu().numpy())
            all_labels.append(label.cpu().numpy())

        correct += (predicted == label).sum().item()

```

```

        total += label.size(0)

    # Accuracy
    accuracy = 100 * correct / total

    # Average loss
    avg_validation_loss = total_loss / len(dataloader)

    # Concatenate all results
    all_probs = np.concatenate(all_probs, axis=0)
    all_preds = np.concatenate(all_preds, axis=0)
    all_labels = np.concatenate(all_labels, axis=0)

    return avg_validation_loss, accuracy, all_labels, all_preds,
           all_probs

```

`display_feature_maps` visualizes the intermediate feature maps produced by the first convolutional layer of the CNN, as an example. The function starts by selecting a specific image from the training dataset, indexed as 7:8 in `images_train`. This slice ensures that only a single image is chosen but maintains the batch dimension. Once the image is correctly formatted, the function sets the model to evaluation mode with `cnn.eval()`. The feature maps are obtained by passing the input image through the first layer of the CNN. This is achieved with `cnn[0](X)`, which extracts the activations from the first convolutional layer. Each feature map is extracted, converted to a *NumPy* array, and displayed.

```

"""Show feature maps from the first convolutional layer"""
def display_feature_maps(cnn, images_train, device, title="Feature
    Maps"):
    X = images_train[7:8] # Seleziona una immagine d'esempio

    X = torch.tensor(X, dtype=torch.float32).to(device)
    X = X.permute(0, 3, 1, 2) # [batch, channels, height, width]

    # Feature map
    cnn.eval()
    with torch.no_grad():
        feature_maps = cnn[0](X) # Passa l'immagine attraverso il
            primo layer

    # Show feature maps
    num_feature_maps = feature_maps.shape[1] # Ottieni il numero di
        feature map
    fig, ax = plt.subplots(int(np.ceil(num_feature_maps / 8)), 8,
        sharex=True, sharey=True, figsize=(16, 8))

```

```

for i in range(num_feature_maps):
    row, col = i // 8, i % 8
    ax[row][col].imshow(feature_maps[0][i].cpu().numpy(), cmap='
        viridis')
    ax[row][col].axis('off')
plt.suptitle(title, fontsize=24)
plt.show()

```

The `plot_metrics` function provides an analysis of the CNN model's classification performance. It focuses on two key aspects: generating a *confusion matrix* and plotting ROC curves for each class. The function begins by filtering the labels and predictions to exclude samples belonging to class 0, which represent "None" category, which is use only for debugging.

The first part of the function generates and visualizes a confusion matrix. The function uses `confusion_matrix` from `sklearn.metrics`, which takes the filtered labels and predictions as inputs. The resulting matrix is then visualized using `ConfusionMatrixDisplay`.

The second part of the function focuses on plotting ROC curves for each class. These are computed using `roc_curve` from `sklearn.metrics`. Once the FPR, TPR, and threshold values are computed, the *area under the curve* (AUC) is calculated using `auc`. The ROC curve for each class is then plotted using `RocCurveDisplay`, which includes the curve and its associated AUC value as a label. These curves are plotted on the same set of axes for easy comparison.

```

def plot_metrics(labels, preds, probs, num_classes):
    # Compute confusion matrix
    mask = (labels != 0)
    filtered_labels = labels[mask]
    filtered_preds = preds[mask]
    filtered_probs = probs[mask, 1:] # Ignore "None" (class 0)
    probabilities

    # Confusion matrix
    cm = confusion_matrix(filtered_labels, filtered_preds, labels=np.
        arange(1, num_classes))
    disp = ConfusionMatrixDisplay(confusion_matrix=cm, display_labels
        =np.arange(1, num_classes))
    fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(10, 10))
    disp.plot(cmap='viridis', ax=ax, xticks_rotation=45)
    plt.title(f"Confusion Matrix")
    plt.show()

    # ROC Curve
    plt.figure(figsize=(10, 8))

```

```

for i in range(1, num_classes):
    # Compute ROC curve and AUC for each class
    fpr, tpr, _ = roc_curve(filtered_labels == i, filtered_probs
       [:, i - 1])
    roc_auc = auc(fpr, tpr)
    RocCurveDisplay(fpr=fpr, tpr=tpr, roc_auc=roc_auc,
        estimator_name=f"Class {i}").plot(ax=plt.gca())

plt.title(f"ROC Curve")
plt.xlabel("False Positive Rate")
plt.ylabel("True Positive Rate")
plt.grid(True, linestyle="--", alpha=0.7)
plt.show()

```

The `load_new_dataset` function is responsible for loading a new FITS dataset for evaluation. It's very similar to `download_and_prepare_dataset`

```

"""Load a new dataset for testing if an already trained model
exists"""
def load_new_dataset(file_path, image_shape=(101, 101, 1)):
    images, labels = [], []
    with FITS.open(file_path) as HDU1:
        for HDU in HDU1:
            if HDU.data is not None:
                images.append(HDU.data.reshape(image_shape))
                label = HDU.header['TYPE'].strip()
                labels.append(int(label))
    images = np.array(images).astype('float32') / 255.0
    labels = np.array(labels, dtype='int64')
    return images, labels

```

The `calculate_re_distribution` function is designed to analyze the possible relationship between the *effective radius* (RE) of celestial objects and the CNN model's prediction accuracy for a specific target class. This function performs two main tasks: first, it categorizes the predictions as correct or incorrect based on whether the model's predicted label matches the true label; second, it visualizes the distributions of RE values for these two categories.

The function begins by initializing two empty lists, `re_values_correct` and `re_values_incorrect`. These lists store the RE values for correctly classified and misclassified samples, respectively. By separating these two categories, the function can later compare their distributions to understand whether the model struggles with objects of certain sizes.

The function requires predictions from the model, so the model is set to evaluation mode with `model.eval()`. The function iterates through the *dataloader*. For each batch,

it performs a forward pass through the model to obtain *logits* and the predicted labels are determined by selecting the class with the highest score using `torch.max`. These predicted labels are stored in the `predictions` list, while the indices of the samples in the dataset are tracked with the `valid_indices` list. Once predictions are generated, the function proceeds to analyze the FITS file specified by `file_path`. Each HDU in the FITS file is examined to extract the true label and RE value from its header. Only valid HDUs are processed.

The function cross-references the `valid_indices` with the predictions made. For each valid sample, it checks whether the model's prediction matches the true label. If the prediction is correct, the sample's RE value is added to the `re_values_correct` list. Otherwise, it is added to the `re_values_incorrect` list. This classification of RE values into correct and incorrect categories forms the basis for the subsequent analysis. After processing all relevant samples, the function visualizes the results using *Matplotlib*. It creates two histograms: one for the distribution of RE values among correctly classified samples and another for misclassified samples. Each histogram displays the frequency of RE values within specific bins, providing insights into whether the model struggles with objects of particular sizes.

```
def calculate_re_distribution(file_path, model, dataloader,
                             target_class=2, device='cpu'):
    """
    Calculates and displays the relationship between the effective
    radius (RE)
    and the correct recognition of images for a target class using
    the model's predictions.

    :param file_path: Path to the FITS file to analyze.
    :param model: PyTorch model to make predictions.
    :param dataloader: DataLoader containing the images to evaluate.
    :param target_class: The class of images to analyze.
    :param device: Device to use for predictions ("cpu" or "cuda").
    """
    re_values_correct = []
    re_values_incorrect = []

    # Get predictions from the model
    model.eval()
    predictions = []
    valid_indices = [] # To keep track of valid indices
    with torch.no_grad():
        for batch_idx, (batch, labels) in enumerate(dataloader):
            batch = batch.to(device)
            outputs = model(batch)
            _, preds = torch.max(outputs, 1)
```

```

    predictions.extend(preds.cpu().numpy())
    # Add valid indices
    valid_indices.extend(batch_idx * dataloader.batch_size +
        i for i in range(len(batch)))

# Open the FITS file
with FITS.open(file_path) as HDU1:
    valid_predictions = {valid_indices[i]: predictions[i] for i
        in range(len(valid_indices))}
    for idx, HDU in enumerate HDU1:
        if \texttt{HDU}.data is not None:
            # Check if the class is target_class and RE is in the
            header
            if 'TYPE' in HDU.header and 'RE' in HDU.header:
                class_type = int(HDU.header['TYPE'])
                if class_type == target_class:
                    re = float(HDU.header['RE'])
                    if re > 0 and idx in valid_predictions: #
                        Avoid invalid values and check index
                        is_correct = (valid_predictions[idx] ==
                            target_class)
                        if is_correct:
                            re_values_correct.append(re)
                        else:
                            re_values_incorrect.append(re)

# Plot the distributions
plt.figure(figsize=(10, 6))

# Correct predictions histogram
plt.subplot(2, 1, 1)
plt.hist(re_values_correct, bins=20, alpha=0.7, color='g',
    edgecolor='k')
plt.title(f"Effective Radius (RE) Distribution - Correct
    Predictions for Class {target_class}", fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel("RE (Effective Radius)", fontsize=12)
plt.ylabel("Count", fontsize=12)
plt.grid(True, linestyle='--', alpha=0.6)

# Incorrect predictions histogram
plt.subplot(2, 1, 2)
plt.hist(re_values_incorrect, bins=20, alpha=0.7, color='r',
    edgecolor='k')
plt.title(f"Effective Radius (RE) Distribution - Incorrect
    Predictions for Class {target_class}", fontsize=14)
plt.xlabel("RE (Effective Radius)", fontsize=12)

```

```
plt.ylabel("Count", fontsize=12)
plt.grid(True, linestyle='--', alpha=0.6)

plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()
```

C.6 Main

`show_sample_images` simply displays random examples from the dataset for qualitative inspection.

```
"""Plots a few example images from the dataset."""
def show_sample_images(images, labels, class_names):
    num_examples = 2
    """Plots a few example images from the dataset."""
    unique_labels = np.unique(labels)
    plt.figure(figsize=(num_examples * len(unique_labels), 5))

    for class_idx, class_label in enumerate(unique_labels):
        # Filtra le immagini della classe corrente
        class_images = images[labels == class_label]

        # Seleziona casualmente `num_examples` immagini dalla classe
        selected_images = class_images[np.random.choice(len(
            class_images), num_examples, replace=False)]

        for i in range(num_examples):
            plt_idx = i * len(unique_labels) + class_idx + 1
            plt.subplot(num_examples, len(unique_labels), plt_idx)
            plt.imshow(selected_images[i].squeeze(), cmap='viridis')
            plt.title(f'{class_names[class_label]}')
            plt.axis('off')

    plt.suptitle("Sample images from the dataset", fontsize=24)
    plt.tight_layout()
    plt.show()
```

The `main` function integrates all components of the script. After defining the paths to key resources, the first task of the main function is loading and preprocessing the dataset using the `download_and_prepare_dataset` function. The dataset is assumed to contain images belonging to four classes: "None", "Star", "Galaxy", and "Background", which are stored in the `class_names` list. The script then displays a few example images from the dataset using the `show_sample_images` function.

To prepare the dataset for training, the `compute_dataset_statistics` and

`create_transforms` are used. The dataset is split into training and testing subsets using the `create_data_loaders` function. Class weights are computed using the `compute_class_weights` function to address any imbalances in the dataset. The weights are then used by `CrossEntropyLoss` during training.

The CNN model is built using the `build_cnn_model` function. The model then is moved to the specified device (e.g., GPU) for training and evaluation. The `summary` function from `torchsummary` is called to display a detailed summary of the model's architecture.

At this point, the function checks whether a pre-trained model already exists. If the file exists, the model's state is loaded using `cnn.load_state_dict(torch.load(model_path))`, allowing the user to skip training and proceed directly to evaluation.

If a pre-trained model is available, the function evaluates it on a new dataset, if such a dataset exists. The `load_new_dataset` function processes this dataset, which is passed through the `evaluate_with_metrics` and `calculate_re_distribution`

If no pre-trained model is found, the function proceeds instead to train the CNN using the `train` function. Once training is complete, the model is saved for future use.

The script also includes functionality to visualize the training process. After training, it plots the training loss and test accuracy curves, providing a visual summary of the model's learning behavior.

Finally, the script concludes by evaluating the trained model on the test set and visualizing its performance using the `plot_metrics` function. Additionally, the `display_feature_maps` function is called to visualize the feature maps learned by the first convolutional layer of the network.

```

if __name__ == "__main__":
    # Setup
    model_path = "cnn_3.pth"
    device = torch.device("cuda" if torch.cuda.is_available() else "cpu")

    images, labels = download_and_prepare_dataset()
    class_names = ["None", "Star", "Galaxy", "Background"]

    show_sample_images(images, labels, class_names)
    # images = add_magnitude_channel(images)
    mean, std = compute_dataset_statistics(images)
    train_transform, test_transform = create_transforms(mean, std)
    train_loader, test_loader = create_data_loaders(images, labels,
                                                    train_transform, test_transform)

    class_weights = compute_class_weights(labels, num_classes=4)

```

```

cnn = build_cnn_model().to(device)
summary(cnn, (1, 101, 101), device=str(device))

# Suppress UndefinedMetricWarning
warnings.filterwarnings("ignore", category=UndefinedMetricWarning
)

if os.path.exists(model_path):
    cnn.load_state_dict(torch.load(model_path))
    print("Model loaded from disk.")

new_dataset_path = "data_new_24_with_Re_5000.FITS"
if os.path.exists(new_dataset_path):
    print("Testing on a new dataset...")
    new_images, new_labels = load_new_dataset(
        new_dataset_path)
    _, _, best_labels, best_preds, best_probs =
        evaluate_with_metrics(
            cnn, DataLoader(CustomDataset(new_images, new_labels,
                transform=test_transform), batch_size=64),
            num_classes=4, device=device)
    print("Testing completed on the new dataset.")
    print("Calculating RE distribution for images of class
        2...")
    calculate_re_distribution(file_path=new_dataset_path,
        model=cnn, dataloader=test_loader, target_class=2,
        device=device)
    print("Distribution calculation completed.")
else:
    print(f"New dataset not found at {new_dataset_path}.
        Using the test set.")
    _, _, best_labels, best_preds, best_probs =
        evaluate_with_metrics(
            cnn, test_loader, num_classes=4, device=device)
else:
    train_losses, test accuracies, best_labels, best_preds,
    best_probs = train(
        cnn, train_loader, test_loader, epochs=100, lr=0.001,
        patience=10, device=device, class_weight=class_weights
    )
    print("Model trained and saved.")
    torch.save(cnn.state_dict(), model_path)

plt.figure(figsize=(12, 4))
plt.subplot(1, 2, 1)

```

```
plt.plot(train_losses, label='Training Loss')
plt.xlabel('Epoch')
plt.ylabel('Loss')
plt.legend()
plt.title('Training Loss Curve')

plt.subplot(1, 2, 2)
plt.plot(test accuracies, label='Test Accuracy')
plt.xlabel('Epoch')
plt.ylabel('Accuracy (%)')
plt.legend()
plt.title('Test Accuracy Curve')
plt.show()

# Overall accuracy at the end of training
print(f"Overall accuracy at the end of training: {
    test accuracies[-1]:.2f}%")

# Plot metrics at the end
plot_metrics(best_labels, best_preds, best_probs, num_classes=4)
display_feature_maps(cnn, train_loader.dataset.images, device)
```

Bibliography

This work has made use of the Early Release Observations (ERO) data from the Euclid mission of the European Space Agency (ESA), 2024, [<https://doi.org/10.57780/esa-qmocz3> | <https://doi.org/10.57780/esa-qmocz3>].

This work made use of Astropy:¹ a community-developed core Python package and an ecosystem of tools and resources for astronomy [36–38] This work made use of astroNN[39, 40].

Galaxy Zoo is described in Lintott et al. 2008, the GalaxyZoo Data Release 2 is described in Lintott et al. 2011, Galaxy Zoo DECaLS Campaign is described in Galaxy Zoo is described in Lintott et al. 2008, the GalaxyZoo Data Release 2 is described in Lintott et al. 2011, Galaxy Zoo DECaLS Campaign is described in Walmsley M. et al. 2021, DESI Legacy Imaging Surveys is described in Dey A. et al., 2019.

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¹<http://www.astropy.org>

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